

D7.4: 4th *Dissemination & communication plan*

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Executive summary

The Dissemination and Communication Plan is a compendium of different complementary actions aimed at promoting the Pro-Enrich project and its results among both the general public and the scientific community.

The plan proposes the overall activities, target groups, stakeholders and target values to be achieved related with the dissemination and communication activities for the entire project period of 42 (originally 36) months.

The 1st edition of the D&C Plan, covering the period from M1 to M12, focused on development of a project website, communication materials including brochures, roll-ups, flyers and fact sheets. During the second half of the first year, activities also included attending conferences and preparation of publications. An overview of activities conducted during the first year of the project can be found in Annex 3. For details see D7.8 - 1st Pro-Enrich event annual report.

The 2nd edition of the D&C Plan, covering the period from M13 to M24, focused on dissemination activities, including promotion of the project and its results at events targeting the general public, the scientific community and industry. For details see D7.9 – 2nd Pro-Enrich event annual report.

The 3rd edition, covering the period M25 to M36, included an updated plan for dissemination activities to be performed during the last year of the project. Due to the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic it was expected that this plan would be changed along the way depending on the developments of the pandemic which were unknown at the time. Alternative possibilities to achieve the D&C targets were thought out along the way. For details see D7.10 - 3rd Pro-Enrich event annual report.

The current 4th edition, covering the period M1 – M42, will provide an overview of the activities performed in the entire project period including the additional six months project extension that were granted as a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic. The communication to the public of the results achieved in the project has been done in a way so not to compromise any IPR for the partners involved. In this context new dissemination materials, including a results poster, brochure, and a roll-up have been developed.

1. Introduction

Dissemination and communication are key activities in Pro-Enrich. This 4th dissemination and communication plan defines the dissemination and communication objectives and includes key messages, target audiences and channels for the project's dissemination and communication activities. Pro-Enrich has a broad audience. A stakeholder analysis has been made and a mix of different tools have been used including a website, social media, posters, roll-ups, flyers, factsheets and different types of publications. All consortium partners have been aware of and committed to ensure good dissemination and communication of the results during the project and will continue this promotion after the end of the project as well.

2. Objectives of the dissemination and communication actions

Pro-Enrich is a research and Innovation (RIA) project providing the European industry with new knowledge about concepts for valorising a range of agricultural residues from rapeseed, olive, citrus fruit and tomatoes for the delivery of high value protein and bioactive products.

The aim of the dissemination and communication actions was to support the project in reaching its objectives. The main objectives of the dissemination and communication activities were:

- To strengthen internal and external communication by defining and describing procedures for communication activities.
- To raise awareness through communication, by informing stakeholders about the project's activities and outcomes of the research and innovation activities.
- To strengthen the connection between primary stakeholders and the Pro-Enrich project.

Dissemination and communication measures were performed both individually and collectively by all partners in close cooperation, targeted at different stakeholders (political, industrial, academic) at various levels (local, regional, national) across the EU.

3. Internal and external communication

3.1. Internal communication

Internal communication activities were planned and executed within Work Package 7 (Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation) led by Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (formerly known as Agro Business Park) with support from Innovarum.

The internal communication objectives for Pro-Enrich were:

- To promote collaboration and dialogue between the Pro-Enrich project partners, as well as with the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking Programme Office.
- To assure a well-organised transmission of information, in a way that all partners can know the state of all activities of the project and, therefore, act together more efficiently
- To keep an effective record of the activities that have been carried out and of the generated information.

- To encourage project partners to promote the distribution of information acquired in the work packages to the defined target audiences.
- To contribute to the BBI JU Programme's communication objectives.

The main internal communication audiences are:

- The Pro-Enrich project partners
- The Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking Programme Office

In order to ensure an effective communication, the Pro-Enrich team have used the following tools:

- Pro-Enrich consortium meetings. A kick-off meeting was organised in the beginning of the project period in Copenhagen. Periodic general assembly meetings in which the advance of the project has been discussed have been held approximately every 6 months. All partners have been invited to these meetings and most have usually attended. Meeting involving partners of particular tasks have been held when needed and work package meetings have been conducted on a regular basis. Before the vaccines were available and when the COVID-19 pandemic made travel impossible, the periodic meetings/general assemblies were held online only. For the final partner meeting and final premarket stimulation event the partners that were able to travel attended physically in Copenhagen and the remaining partners attended online.
- Mailing lists. A general mailing list with all partners for general project communication and sub-lists was created.
- Digital networking, including with the BBI Joint Undertaking Programme Office. Online blogs and social media networks have been used where relevant.
- Restricted access area. A password-protected common space for the partners has been set up on the cloud (Microsoft Teams, <https://teams.microsoft.com>, see screenshot below) where project documents and other relevant information are available. This was intended to ease collaboration between partners on the elaboration of documents and has also aided in keeping record of all activities. DTI was responsible for establishing the restricted access area and for inviting project members. Likewise, DTI will keep the documents on record for an extended period after project end.

Figure 1. Screenshot of "Microsoft Teams" where the project's information is stored

3.2. External communication

External communication activities have been planned and executed within Work Package 7 (Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation) led by Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (formerly known as Agro Business Park).

The external communication objectives for Pro-Enrich were:

- To introduce the Pro-Enrich project to the relevant stakeholders, policy makers and the general public, informing about its progress, outcomes and benefits.
- To raise awareness about protein scarcity and bio-based alternatives and promote the Pro-Enrich solution.
- To inform about alternative protein sources and promote circular economy as well as the revalorisation of rapeseed, olive, tomato and citrus fruit side streams.

The main external communication audiences were raw material providers (olive oil, rapeseed and fruits and vegetables producers), end users (cosmetic, pharmaceutical, food and feed manufacturers) and researchers (academic researchers, RTOs and R&D managers). Other external audiences include policy makers, institutions, and the general public. A detailed external communication plan for each target group can be found in Annex 1.

In order to reach these target audiences, the following tools have been used:

- **Pro-Enrich website.** <http://www.pro-enrich.eu> has been used as the main communication tool. The website contains general information on the project and the consortium, news regarding the project, public deliverables and downloadable visual information such as brochures, factsheets and leaflets.

- **Social networks.** Updates on the website have in many cases been reflected on the project partners' social networks: Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube and other more specialised networks like ResearchGate or SlideShare.
- **Brochures and fact sheets.** These contained the project's main data as well as information on the consortium.
- **Publications.** These, depending on the target audience specific for each publication, have been featured in newspapers and journals or more scientific/technical journals.
- **Events:**
 - Final event to disseminate project results: This was held October 14th 2021 to present the results and put spotlight on the next step that we are facing; namely scaling up our processes. To attract a wider audience we chose to name the event "[From residue to revenue – Scaling up biosolutions](#)" to shed light on the general challenges of scaling up biosolutions.
 - Conferences, lectures, seminars and webinars of relevance to the project have been targeted for presentations of the project.
 - Fairs and exhibitions have been attended.
- Networking, face-to-face interviews and direct contacts have been ongoing throughout the project period.

More detailed information about D&C activities and the tools used to reach the different target audiences, can be found in Annex 2.

Figure 2. Screenshot of Pro-Enrich website, <http://www.pro-enrich.eu>

4. Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plan (DMP) covers the following issues:

- Data Summary
- FAIR data

- Allocation of resources
- Data security
- Ethical aspects
- Other issues

The DMP aims to ensure that Pro-Enrich activities will be compliant with the H2020 Open Access policy and the recommendations of the Open Research Data pilot.

The DMP of Pro-Enrich, coherently with the EU guidelines¹, describes the data management procedures according to the FAIR principles². FAIR stands for findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. Commonly identified as the four main features of project research data, they are fundamentals for allowing their maximum knowledge circulation as well as final return on investment (“scientific ROI”). This is in line with the guidelines provided by the EC in several documents: Horizon 2020 Programme, Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research.

The detailed DMP of Pro-Enrich can be found in ANNEX 5.

5. Communication strategy

5.1. Key messages

Key questions that have been answered in almost every piece of communication are:

What is the main objective of Pro-Enrich?

To develop novel functional proteins and bioactive ingredients from rapeseed, olive, tomato and citrus fruit side streams.

Why is it important to achieve this?

Because the demand for protein and other bioactive compounds can no longer be met through conventional, mainly animal, sources, and, in addition, the manufacture of these compounds has significant negative environmental impacts.

How will Pro-Enrich meet this objective?

Pro-Enrich will develop a flexible biorefinery approach capable of processing a range of agricultural residues. Pro-Enrich will optimise existing biomass fractionation technologies and validate novel extraction approaches beyond the current state of the art to isolate and purify proteins, polyphenols, dietary fibres and pigments.

¹ Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 (Version 3.0, 26 July 2016):

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

² The FAIR data principles (Force11 discussion forum) <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

What are the effective applications of the results obtained from the Pro-Enrich project?

Pro-Enrich aims to produce proteins and bioactive ingredients that will be used for the production of food ingredients, pet food, cosmetics and adhesives.³

5.2. Tone of communication

The tone of all Pro-Enrich-related communication has been informative, descriptive and positive in order to inform and explain the facts to the audience. It has been polite, but not too formal, and non-political. This tone was intended to highlight the importance of developing systems that will help palliate protein scarcity, of having other means to produce proteins and bioactive compounds without compromising the environment and the benefits that this will entail for the industry and the European economy.

6. Target audiences of dissemination & communication actions

6.1. Identify target groups and key stakeholders for addressing external communication

The Pro-Enrich partners have worked to stimulate engagement and interaction with stakeholders who have the potential or a direct interest in learning about the project's results which could have an impact on their work.

Stakeholders in Pro-Enrich are classified in three categories, *key players*, *supporters* and *tertiary stakeholders*.

Figure 2. Stakeholder classification

Primary stakeholders (key players)

- Raw material providers (olive, rapeseed, fruit and vegetable producers), end users (cosmetic, pharma/nutraceutical, food and feed companies), researchers (academic researchers, RTOs and R&D managers).

Secondary stakeholders (supporters)

- Policy makers (at regional, national and EU level)

Tertiary stakeholders

- General public

For details concerning the “purpose” and the “message” to the individual stakeholders see Annex 1.

³ After the project began, we have added the nutraceuticals and an end user in our communications – specifically for the hesperidin and lycopene products developed in the project.

7. Dissemination & communication actions proposed for each target audience

Pro-Enrich has a broad audience. In order to reach different types of audience, a number of specific D&C actions have been performed in the Pro-Enrich project. The actions include development of a dedicated website, use of social media, manufacture of brochures and factsheets, publications, attending conferences, organizing a final event and more.

The individual actions for the different target audience/groups are defined in the following. An even more detailed plan, which covers the entire project period of 42 months is found in Annex 3.

7.1. All target groups (including general public)

PRO-ENRICH WEBSITE & BLOG

A dedicated Pro-Enrich website has been made <http://www.pro-enrich.eu>. The website is maintained by Food & Bio Cluster Denmark and includes the following sections:

- **Home page:** Project overview, including a group picture with each partner's representatives (taken at the kick of meeting day) and information about "latest news".
- **About the project:** Short description and facts about the Pro-Enrich project
- **Partners:** Each partner's logo (hyperlinked to their own websites), name, and country of origin.
- **Workplan:** A PERT diagram and a short description of individual work packages. Pictures and contact details to individual work package leaders is provided.
- **News:** The website includes a blog where relevant information concerning Pro-Enrich activities has continuously been posted.
- **Dissemination:** Developed dissemination materials including roll-ups, posters, brochures and a fact-sheet which can be downloaded.
- **Contact:** Contact details to project coordinator Anne Christine Hastrup Steenkjaer (DTI) and dissemination manager Louise Krogh Johnson (FBCD) is provided.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - 5.000 hits,
 - At least 35 posts on the blog
- Lead Partner:
 - Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (FBCD) is responsible for running and maintaining the Pro-Enrich website.
- Status at the end of the project: Targets reached with 8842 hits and 35 blog posts.

WEB 2.0 TOOLS

The following Web 2.0 tools have been used for dissemination with a visual approach: Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - >60 posts
- Lead Partner:
 - Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
- Status at the end of the project: Target reached with 150 posts.

BROCHURES AND FACT SHEETS

Roll-ups, posters, brochures and factsheets have been developed as part of the deliveries “D.7-6 - Initial Dissemination & communication materials package” (M6) and “D7.7 “Final Dissemination & communication materials package” (M40). The materials can be downloaded in the “dissemination” section on the Pro-Enrich website, <https://www.pro-enrich.eu/dissemination>.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - 6 roll-ups,
 - 6.000 flyers
 - 1.400 factsheets
- Lead Partner:
 - Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
- Status at the end of the project: The COVID-19 pandemic drastically reduced the opportunities to participate in physical events and show or hand out printed materials, so we have deliberately not reached the targets here. We have created two roll ups of which four were printed and used by multiple partners, two flyers/brochures (one about the project and one with results) which were printed in 2200 copies, and a factsheet which was printed in 1600 copies. Furthermore, we have created three posters and printed seven copies. We have also created five project dissemination videos available via the same [link](#).

PUBLICATION IN NEWSPAPERS AND JOURNALS

Pro-Enrich activities and results have been published at local, national, international level (Euractive.com; EuroNews, EUagenda) as well as relevant journals within food, rapeseed, olives, tomatoes and citrus. The (number of) publications have been collected and updated in a “planning document”. The “planning document” has been a “living document” being continuously updated.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - >30 articles
- Lead Partner:
 - Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
- Status at the end of the project: The Pro-Enrich partners have had the project featured 44 times in various journals and news channels incl. Biotech Spain, S4C Daily News for Youngsters (BBC), Ingeniøren (The Engineer) and more.

FINAL EVENT

To ensure dissemination of the final project results, Pro-Enrich organized a final event, hosted by DTI on October 14th, 2021 (M42), which also included a pre-market stimulation event in the afternoon. In order to reach the broadest possible audience, and to make up for people not allowed to travel due to corona, the event was a hybrid event also available via streaming. The title of the event was “From residue to revenue – Scaling up biosolutions” in order to put spotlight on the next steps after the project results had been achieved. This included technical challenges as well as the financial side of investments and funding.

Click [here](#) to see the programme.

Click [here](#) to read the press release published about the event.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - 100 participants and connections
- Lead Partner:
 - Food & Bio Cluster Denmark was mainly responsible for organizing the final event, and DTI was co-organiser and contributed equally.
- Status at the end of the project: 91 people were signed up for the event in total and approx. 75 people attended the event. Of these 36 people attended the event physically – most of them were from Denmark.

Picture 1: Jose M. Pinilla giving his presentation at final event on October 14th, 2021

EC DISSEMINATION ROUTES

The consortium partners have ensured that the excellent dissemination tools provided by the EC for dissemination to European citizens, industry and the scientific community were utilised in the project. Details of the project were made available for articles to be included in European electronic and paper publications such as research*eu.

Pro-Enrich information is available on the following websites (in addition to www.pro-enrich.eu):

- Bio-Based Industries (BBI)
 - <https://www.bbi-europe.eu/projects/pro-enrich>
- CORDIS
 - <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/218393/factsheet/en>
- Welch government services and information
 - <https://gov.wales/sites/default/files/publications/2019-03/horizon-2020-annual-report-2018.pdf>
- European Policies Research Centre Delft
 - <http://www.bizkaia.eus/fitxategiak/05/Ogasuna/Europa-Proiektuak/dokumentuak/From%20Smart%20Growth%20to%20Smarter%20Europe.pdf?hash=ac33f800461c2bf57a725d07351c1516>
- OpenAIRE Explore
 - https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020::b04902be9adf3d6d6ecf2bb02a54482a
- Biorefine Cluster Europe
 - <https://www.biorefine.eu/projects/pro-enrich/>

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - Presence of a project webpage
- Lead Partner
 - Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
- Status at the end of the project: Pro-Enrich has had a project webpage continuously updated through the course of the project and has additionally been featured on partner websites and the ones mentioned above.

7.2. Research and scientific community

PUBLICATION IN JOURNALS

The research organisations and universities in the consortium have authored scientific papers describing the scientific and technical achievements of the project for publication in peer-reviewed journals, including Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies, BioResources, Journal of Natural Products, and more. When possible, the research organisations have used “gold” (open access) or green” (selfarchiving) access for depositing peer reviewed research and final manuscripts arising from their activities in the Pro-Enrich project, in line with the EC’s Open Access Pilot initiative and allowing the scientific community greater access to the knowledge generated in the project.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - >5 papers published
- Lead Partner
 - Bangor University
- Status at the end of the project: Despite significant efforts, the consortium has at this stage only had three papers published out of 13 submissions. Five papers are pending approval at the time of submission of this deliverable and more are still in preparation and will be submitted before the end of the year and will in this case be included in the final report.
 - Papers approved for publication
 - [Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies](#)
 - [Journal of Natural products](#)
 - [Molecules Special Issue: Antioxidants from Natural Sources: Separation and Characterization](#)

WEB 2.0 TOOLS

ResearchGate, SlideShare, YouTube, LinkedIn

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - >60 posts,
 - 1500 Visualisations
- Lead Partner
 - Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
- Status at the end of the project: Target reached with 150 posts.

LECTURES, WEBINARS

Use of project and its results in lectures and as a subject for universities. The specific content for lectures was defined as the projects progressed and lectures were given at University of Zagreb (2019), Technical University of Braunschweig and Salzburg University among others.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - At least 4 lectures
- Lead Partner
 - Bangor University
- Status at the end of the project: Target reached with eight lectures given within the course of the project in different countries, incl. at the University of Zagreb, the Forest Products Laboratory in Madison, Wisconsin, USA, Salzburg University and Eberswalde University in Germany.

PARTICIPATION IN BROAD EVENTS

The events intended here were Open day at the Universities, Researchers' Nights (each year in September), and Knowledge Open Festivals. However, COVID-19 reduced the possibilities for attending the broadest type of events, especially those including the general public. However, Pro-Enrich partners managed to attend 12 broad events none the less (physical and virtual), incl. Danish Bio-Economy Conference (2018, 2019), Natural Resources Wales Workshop (2019), The Future of Food – Unlocking the benefits of Scotland's circular economy (2020) and RTO Innovation Summit (2020).

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - At least 10 events attended
- Lead Partner
 - DTI
- Status at the end of the project: Target reached with 12 events attended.

EXHIBITIONS AND CONFERENCES

The Pro-Enrich partners have delivered presentations at scientific conferences and exhibited at physical and virtual exhibitions describing their project activities and results obtained during the project to target the scientific and technical communities, incl. Food Festival, Bringing Value to Agrobiomass, Circular Bioeconomy Days, International conference of polyphenols, and more.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - At least 15 events attended
- Lead Partner
 - DTI
- Status at the end of the project: Target reached with 16 events attended.

7.3. Industries

PARTICIPATION AT CONFERENCES, SEMINARS, TRADE SHOWS, EXHIBITIONS, PAPERS, POSTERS AND PPT PRESENTATION, FACE-TO-FACE MEETINGS

The consortium has actively promoted the Pro-Enrich technology and project by attending exhibitions and conferences. The partners have used exhibition stands at national and international tradeshows to promote the Pro-Enrich developments to industry and end users. A list of exhibitions and conferences is provided in Annex 3 (planning document).

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - At least 20 events attended
- Lead Partner
 - DTI
- Status at the end of the project: Target reached with 26 events of this kind attended.

ARTICLES AND FEATURES IN INDUSTRIAL JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES

To stimulate interest in the take up and dissemination of the new Pro-Enrich processing methods, product range and subsequent applications, the project partners have produced articles for publication in trade journals relevant to developments in the project, incl. Olive Oil Times, Mundo del Agronomo, New Food, and more.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - >10 articles
- Lead Partner
 - InnoRenew
- Status at the end of the project: Target reached with 11 articles published.

PROMOTION THROUGH PROFESSIONAL ORGANISATIONS

The consortium partners have used the following professional bodies (and their trade publications), networks, trade associations and European Technology Platforms (ETP) as a means to disseminate the results and benefits of the Pro- Enrich project throughout the EU, as well as the BBI platform.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - >10 meetings,
 - >150 contacts
- Lead Partner
 - DTI
- Status at the end of the project: Target reached with 10 meetings and 150+ contacts.

PRE-MARKET STIMULATION ACTIVITIES

The consortium partners have organised a series of activities to support pre-market dissemination of the project results targeted at a range of chemical companies and manufacturers of end products (e.g. food, feeds, proteins, antioxidants, adhesives, resins, etc). These technology demonstrator events were intended to be held at the industrial partners various sites, but COVID-19 put a stop to this plan. Innovarum, DTI and FBCD proposed that four

of the events were converted to videos and webinars instead that were targeted the food, cosmetics, adhesives, and processing industries. These videos were created as a lasting dissemination product that remains available to viewers after the end of the project period. Furthermore, pre-market stimulation webinars were organised in which these videos were premiered, and presentations were held about the project results followed by Q&A sessions. Each webinar attracted approx. 20-30 participants. Articles were posted about each webinar on the website.

- Cosmetics industry: [Upcycling citrus and tomato biomass for high value applications](#) (30.06.21).
- Processing industry: [Processing of rapeseed meal and other raw materials for protein extraction](#) (01.07.21).
- Adhesives industry: [Replacing petrochemicals in adhesives – Our experience with rapeseed protein](#) (06.07.21).
- Food industry: [Upcycling food waste into new proteins and functional ingredients](#) (12.07.21).

The fifth and final pre-market stimulation event was organised as part of the final conference at DTI where partners had a physical booth at the conference venue that people could visit after lunch and where there were guided tours to the DTI pilot plant. The partners that were not able to attend physically were present via Teams on laptops (see picture).

Picture 2: The booths of Emmelev (left) and CHIMAR (right) at the fifth pre-market stimulation event on October 14th, 2021

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - >5 activities
- Lead Partner
 - Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
- Status at the end of the project: Target achieved with five pre-market stimulation events organised.

7.4. Existing networks

NETWORKING, DELIVERY OF AD HOC NEWSLETTERS, CONTRIBUTION TO THE EXISTING NEWSLETTERS

Pro-Enrich has communicated broadly to industries using established communication channels, incl. Innovation Network for Bioresources, Environment Technology Associations (DETA), Network for Polymers, Agripa, and more.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - At least 15 new connections established
- Lead Partner
 - Innovarum
- Status at the end of the project: Target reached with 17 new connections established.

7.5. Political organizations

DIRECT CONTACTS, PERSONAL INVITATIONS, CONFERENCES AND OTHER EVENTS

The focus has been on regional, national and EU levels by targeting ministries, regional authorities and EU wide organisations and informing them about the perspectives in the project. The entry point has been contacts already established by the various partners with their local political networks for example: the Ministry of Research and Innovation in Denmark, Expert Groups, etc.

- Target values to be reached along the whole lifespan of the project:
 - >2 political representatives participating in project related events.
- Lead Partner
 - DTI
- Status at the end of the project: During the course of the project partners have had dialogue with political figures and organisations seven times where the Pro-Enrich project was mentioned.

8. Protocols for harmonising dissemination and communication in the Pro-Enrich project

8.1. Procedures

Harmonisation in the way all the consortium members carry out their communication and dissemination actions related to the Pro-Enrich project was essential to have a coherent and powerful appearance. Since Pro-Enrich counts 16 partners, in order to facilitate this task, we designed a series of templates for the expected types of communication and dissemination actions that were undertaken (enclosed in Annex 4). They are:

- Template for deliverables
- Template for PowerPoint presentations
- Template for the meeting agendas
- Template for the meeting minutes
- Template for posters in congresses and fairs

These templates have been circulated among all the consortium partners and it was recommended for all to follow them as much as possible in dissemination and communication actions.

8.2. Project's visual identity elements

The project's visual identity was designed by the DTI, and consists of the following logo:

Figure 3. Pro-Enrich official logo

When considered necessary the visual communication can as well be done only with the logo synthesis:

Figure 4. Pro-Enrich's synthesis of official logo

REFERRING CORRECTLY TO THE PROJECT'S FUNDING BODIES

In all dissemination and communication material, it was stated that the project has received funding from H2020 and BBI. The following logos and text were included in all templates for PowerPoint presentations.

“This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 792050”

Figure 5. Reference to project's funding bodies

9. Annexes

Annex 1 – Pro-Enrich D&C target groups, purpose and message

Annex 2 – Dissemination and communication activities

Annex 3 – Pro-Enrich dissemination and communication planning document

Annex 4 - Templates for harmonising dissemination and communication activities

Annex 5 – Data Management Plan

Annex 6 – Final event programme

Annex 1 – Pro-Enrich D&C target groups, purpose and message

Range	Target groups		Purpose	Message
Key players	Raw material providers	<i>Olive oil producers</i>	Call the attention of this segment to create a pool of raw materials providers interested in being involved in the project in future stages.	Alternative way to manage and valorise the by-products that are currently underutilized (from a social, economic and environmental perspective).
		<i>Rapeseed oil producers</i>		
		<i>Fruits and vegetables producers</i>		
	End users	<i>Cosmetics companies</i>	Call the attention of this segment, since those are the adopters of the products obtained through the Pro-Enrich process, in order to create a pool of validators to be involved in future stages of the project.	New clean source of proteins and phenolic compounds to be used in their industrial processes.
		<i>Pharmaceutical companies</i>		
		<i>Food companies</i>		
		<i>Feed companies</i>		
	Researchers	<i>Academic researchers</i>	Researchers are a key target in order to disseminate knowledge within the community of practice in bio-refinery and protein extraction. They will be key in supporting the take off of our new ideas and solutions.	New clean source of proteins and phenolic compounds and new processes are tested to pave the way for new process in the field.
		<i>RTOs</i>		
		<i>R&D managers</i>		
Secondary stakeholders “Supporters”	Policy makers	<i>Regional</i>	Policy makers within agriculture, food, industrial and innovation policies	Alternative plant based alternatives to proteins and bioactive ingredients are

Range	Target groups		Purpose	Message
		<i>National</i>	will be key at all levels to foster an environment in favour of alternative proteins and biorefinery technologies.	available and make sense from an economic, societal and environmental standpoint and should be supported.
		<i>EU level</i>		
Tertiary stakeholders	General public		The general public is not per se a target group for dissemination results but will be a key target group for communication activities.	Waste can become value.

Annex 2 – Dissemination and communication activities

Target audience	Dissemination activities		Start month	Indicator to measure the impact	Target Value
All target groups (including general public)	Pro-Enrich website & Blog	Permanent web hub with downloadable public deliverables and results. The site will be used to distribute the project newsletter on a “sign-up” basis.	1	No. of hits and posts	5.000 hits, at least 35 posts on the blog
	Web tools 2.0	Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube. Dissemination with a visual approach.	2	No. of posts	>60 posts,
	Brochures and fact sheets	Digital and printed format	3	No. of flyers/factsheets distributed	6 roll-ups, 3.000 flyers, 1.400 factsheets
	Publication in newspapers and journals	At local, national, international level (Euractive.com; EuroNews, EUagenda) as well as relevant journals within food, rapeseed, olives, tomatoes, citrus	1	No. of articles	>30 articles,
	Final event	Available also in streaming to reach the broadest possible audience	36	No. of participants and new connections	100 participants, and connections
	EC Dissemination routes	The consortium partners will ensure that the excellent dissemination tools provided by the EC for dissemination to European citizens, industry and the scientific community will be utilised in the project. Details of the project will be made available for articles to be included in European electronic and paper publications such as research*eu.	6	Visibility on EU websites	Presence of a project page

Target audience	Dissemination activities		Start month	Indicator to measure the impact	Target Value
Research and scientific community + Academics	Publication in Journals	<p>The research organisations and universities in the consortium will author scientific articles describing the scientific and technical achievements of the project for publication in peer-reviewed journals, for example: International Journal of Recycling of Organic Waste in Agriculture; Waste and Biomass Valorisation; Biochemical Engineering Journal; Biotechnology and Engineering; Industrial Crops and Products; Biorefinery; Bioresources; Journal of renewable materials...</p> <p>When possible, the research organisations will preferably use “gold” (open access) or green” (self-archiving) access for depositing peer reviewed research and final manuscripts arising from their activities in the Pro-Enrich project, in line with the EC’s Open Access Pilot initiative and allowing the scientific community greater access to the knowledge generated in the project.</p>	Results obtained	No. of papers published	>5 papers published
	Web tools 2.0	ResearchGate, SlideShare, YouTube, LinkedIn	4	No. of posts and visualisations	>60 posts, 1500 visualisations
	Lectures, webinars	Use of project and its results in lectures and as a subject for universities	36	No. of lectures	At least 4 lectures
	Participation in broad events	Open day at the Universities, Researchers' Nights (each year in September), and Knowledge Open Festivals	9	No. of events attended	At least 10 events attended
	Exhibitions and conferences	The research partners will deliver presentations at conferences describing their activities and results obtained during the project to target the scientific and technical communities, for example: at major international conferences such as International Consultative Group for Research on Rapeseed. 15th GCIRC	6	No. of events attended	At least 15 events attended

Target audience	Dissemination activities		Start month	Indicator to measure the impact	Target Value
		<p>Rapeseed Congress, Berlin, June 16-20, 2019. XV International Symposium on Processing Tomato - XIII World Processing Tomato Congress. Location, Athens (Greece) June 11, 2018.</p>			
Industries	<p>Participation at conferences, seminars, trade shows, exhibitions, Papers, posters and ppt presentation Face-to-face meetings</p>	<p>The consortium will actively promote the Pro-Enrich technology and project by attending the following exhibitions and conferences. The industrial partners will use exhibition stands at national and international tradeshows to promote the Pro-Enrich developments to industry and end users.</p> <p><i>Preliminary list:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FEICA European Adhesive & Sealant Conference and EXPO; • EURAD – European conference on Adhesion and Adhesive; • Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy Conference; Feed Additives; • Bio-Based Live Europe (BBI JU is associate sponsor in 2017); • European Biomass Conference; • THE LARGEST FOOD TRADE FAIR IN THE NORDIC COUNTRIES. Denmark, Herning Foodexpo 18. - 20. March 2018; • ANUGA FOOD TECH, Köln, Marts 2018, Germany; • International Conference on Renewable Resources & Biorefineries, RRB 14, Ghent 30. May-1. June 2018 • ANUGA FOOD FAIR, Cologne, October 2019, Germany; • Ligna fair, Hannover, May 2019; • Nutrifair, Fredericia, Denmark. • Protein summit, October 2018, Reims, France. 	3	No. of events attended and presentation/ speeches	At least 20 events attended

Target audience	Dissemination activities		Start month	Indicator to measure the impact	Target Value
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food tech 2018, Barcelona, Spain. • Food Ingredients Europe, Paris 2019 • Vitafoods, May 2018, Geneve, Switzerland • ALIBETOPIAS, Spain (www.alibetopias.es). • Fruit logistica (Berlin) (2018,2019,2020) • Fruti Attraction (Madrid) (2018,2019,2020) • Alimentaria (Barcelona) (2018,2019,2020) 				
	Articles and features in industrial journals and magazines	In order to stimulate interest in the take up and dissemination of the new Pro-Enrich processing methods, product range and subsequent applications, the project's industrial partners will produce articles publication in trade journals relevant to developments in the project.	3	No. of articles published	>10 articles
	Dissemination activities		Start month	Indicator to measure the impact	Target Value
	Promotion through professional organisations	The consortium partners will use the following profession bodies (and their "trade" publications), networks, trade associations and European Technology Platforms (ETP) as a means to disseminate the results and benefits of the Pro-Enrich project throughout the EU, as well as the BBI platform.	1	No. of meetings attended, No. of contacts gained	>10meetings, >150 contacts

Target audience	Dissemination activities		Start month	Indicator to measure the impact	Target Value
Pre-market stimulation activities		The consortium partners will organise a series of activities to support pre-market dissemination of the project results targeted at a range of chemical companies and manufacturers of end products (e.g. food, feeds, proteins, antioxidants, adhesives, resins, etc). Technology demonstrator events will be held at the industrial partners various sites, press releases will be made available on the project website and distributed to trade journals and brochures prepared detailing the Pro-Enrich developments in materials and the provision of bio-derived sustainable solutions.	20	No. of activities organised	>5 activities
Existing networks	Networking, delivery of ad hoc newsletters, contribution to the existing newsletters	Preliminary list of networks: ESWET ; EIP-AGRI; COPA-COGECA; RAMIRAN (part of the ESCORENA network); CGIAR – FAO; GBEP - Global Bioenergy Partnership; The Knowledge Centre for Agriculture; International Network for Environmental management (INEM).	4	No. of connections	At least 15 new connections established
Political organizations	Direct contacts, personal invitations, conferences and other events	The focus will be on regional, national and EU levels by targeting ministries, regional authorities and EU wide organisations. The entry point will be contacts already established by the various partners with their local political networks for example: the Ministry of Research and Innovation in Denmark, Expert Groups, etc.	12	Media coverage, keynote speech	>2 political representatives participate in the project related events.

Annex 3 – Pro-Enrich dissemination and communication planning document

The “planning document” has been a “living document” which was updated continuously throughout the project period. The following information shows status at the end of the project (M42).

Activity overview

1 - All target groups (including general public)	
1A	Pro-Enrich website & Blog
1B	Web 2.0 tools
1C	Brochures and fact sheets
1D	Publication in newspapers and journals
1E	Final event
1F	EC Dissemination routes
2 - Research and scientific community	
2A	Publication in Journals
2B	Web 2.0 tools
2C	Lectures, webinars
2D	Participation in broad events
2E	Exhibitions and conferences
3 - Industries	
3A	Participation at conferences, seminars, trade shows, exhibitions, Papers, posters and ppt presentation Face-to-face meetings
3B	Articles and features in industrial journals and magazines
3C	Promotion through professional organisations
3D	Pre-market stimulation activities
4 - Existing networks	
4A	Networking, delivery of ad hoc newsletters, contribution to the existing newsletters

Partner and activity overview

Activity	DTI	BU	INR	GEA	AC	TZ	FBCD	EML	LT	MF	CHM	INV	JC	MRS	NTC	T&L
1A	x	x	x	x	x	x	X	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
1B	x	x	x				X					x				
1C	x	x	x	x	x	x	X	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
1D	x	x					X		x			x			x	
1E	x	x	x				X					x				
1F	x						X									
2A	x	X	x													
2B	x						X					x				
2C	x	X	x													
2D	X	x					x					x				
2E	X	x	x													
3A	X	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
3B	x	x	X													
3C	X						x					x				
3D		x	x				X					x				
4A	x	x	x				x					X				
5A	X	x	x				x					x				
PM	3	2.45	5	1	1	2	20	1	4	1	2	11	1	1	1	1
X	Lead partner															
x	Contributing partner															

Note: Leitao (LT) assumed the responsibilities of Vertech (WP6 leader) following their termination from the project in September 2020.

1.A. Target audience - All target groups (including general public)

Dissemination activity	Pro-Enrich website & Blog Permanent web hub with downloadable public deliverables and results. The site will be used to distribute the project newsletter on a "sign-up" basis.
Start month:	1
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of hits and posts
Target Value	5.000 hits, at least 35 posts on the blog
Lead Partner	Agro Business Park
Contributing Partners	All
Additional Information	Link to homepage http://www.pro-enrich.eu

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

HOMEPAGE	TARGET VALUE	STATUS (M42)
Hits	5000	8842
Posts on the blog	35	35

1.B. Target audience - All target groups (including general public)

Dissemination activity	Web 2.0 tools Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, LinkedIN. Dissemination with a visual approach.
Start month:	2
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of posts
Target Value	>60 posts
Lead Partner	Agro Business Park
Contributing Partners	DTI, Innovarum, InnoRenew, Bangor University, all partners

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

POST NO.	WHEN	WHO	WHERE	LINK
1	01.05.18	INV	Website	Link
2	03.05.18	ABP	LinkedIN	Link
3	03.05.18	INR	Facebook	Link
4	03.05.18	INR	Facebook	Link
5	03.05.18	INR	Twitter	Link
6	28.05.18	ABP	LinkedIN	Link
7	05.07.18	BU	Twitter	Link
8	06.07.18	INV	Website	Link
9	20.07.18	BU	Twitter	Link
10	03.09.18	INR	LinkedIn	Link
11	03.09.18	INR	Twitter	Link

12	03.09.18	INR	Facebook	Link
13	27.09.18	INV	Twitter	Link
14	15.10.18	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
15	16.10.18	INV	Twitter	Link
16	25.10.18	BU	Twitter	Link
17	25.10.18	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
18	29.10.18	INR	Facebook	Link
19	29.10.18	INR	Twitter	Link
20	29.10.18	INR	LinkedIn	Link
21	14.11.18	INV	Twitter	Link
22	15.11.18	INV	Twitter	Link
23	19.11.18	INR	Facebook	Link
24	19.11.18	INR	Twitter	Link
25	26.11.18	INV	Website	Link
26	29.11.18	INV	LinkedIn	Link
27	19.11.18	INR	LinkedIn	Link
28	10.01.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link
29	15.01.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
30	17.01.19	BU	Twitter	Link
31	22.01.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link
32	31.01.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link
33	04.02.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link
34	11.02.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link
35	14.02.19	VER	Facebook	Link
36	14.02.19	VER	LinkedIn	Link
37	01.03.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
38	11.03.19	INV	Twitter	Link
39	11.03.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
40	15.03.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
41	20.03.19	INV	Twitter	Link
42	25.03.19	INV	Twitter	Link
43	25.03.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
44	27.03.19	BU	Twitter	Link
45	01.04.19	GEA	LinkedIn	Link
46	02.04.19	INV	Twitter	Link
47	02.04.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
48	10.04.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
49	12.04.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
50	14.07.19	BU	Twitter	Link
51	15.04.19	INV	Twitter	Link
52	15.04.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
53	23.04.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
54	24.05.19	BU	Twitter	Link
55	11.06.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
56	15.06.19	VER	LinkedIn	Link
57	20.06.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
58	07.08.19	BU	Youtube	Link
59	28.08.19	INR	Twitter	Link

60	03.09.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
61	06.09.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
62	06.09.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
63	16.09.19	BU	Twitter	Link
64	12.09.19	BU	Twitter	Link
65	12.09.19	BU	Twitter	Link
66	01.10.19	BU	Twitter	Link
67	19.11.19	NAT	LinkedIn	Link
68	20.11.19	VER	LinkedIn	Link
69	21.11.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
70	05.12.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
71	20.12.19	DTI	LinkedIn	Link
72	14.01.20	INV	Twitter	Link
73	14.01.20	INV	LinkedIn	Link
74	12.02.20	BU	Twitter	Link
75	14.02.20	INV	LinkedIn	Link
76	03.03.20	INV	Twitter	Link
77	03.03.20	INV	LinkedIn	Link
78	14.04.20	INV	Twitter	Link
79	14.04.20	INV	LinkedIn	Link
80	17.4.20	BU	Twitter	Link
81	21.04.20	INV	Twitter	Link
82	21.04.20	INV	LinkedIn	Link
83	24.04.20	NTC	LinkedIn	Link
84	23.04.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
85	23.04.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
86	24.04.20	NTC	LinkedIn	Link
87	24.04.20	NTC	LinkedIn	Link
88	29.04.20	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
89	29.04.20	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
90	30.04.20	INR	LinkedIn	Link
91	30.04.20	INR	Twitter	Link
92	30.04.20	INR	Facebook	Link
93	25.05.20	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
94	25.05.20	ABP	Facebook	Link
95	04.06.20	INV	Twitter	Link
96	02.07.20	INV	Twitter	Link
97	14.07.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
98	21.07.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
99	21.08.20	BU	Twitter	Link
100	03.09.20	INV	Twitter	Link
101	03.09.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
102	07.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
103	08.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
104	15.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
105	19.10.20	BU	Twitter	Link
106	21.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
107	27.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link

108	29.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
109	06.11.20	INV	Twitter	Link
110	10.11.20	GEA	LinkedIn	Link
111	10.11.20	GEA	LinkedIn	Link
112	10.11.20	GEA	Facebook	Link
113	10.11.20	GEA	Facebook	Link
114	10.11.20	GEA	Twitter	Link
115	24.11.20	FBCD	LinkedIn	Link
		Welch		
		Government		
116	24.02.21	Office, Brussels	Twitter	Link
117	08.03.21	Natac	LinkedIn	Link
118	10.04.21	DTI	LinkedIn	Link
119	01.03.21	CHI	LinkedIn	Link
120	17.05.21	INV	LinkedIn	Link
121	18.05.21	CHI	LinkedIn	Link
122	15.06.21	FBCD	LinkedIn	Link
123	15.06.21	FBCD	LinkedIn	Link
124	16.06.21	INV	Twitter	Link
125	16.06.21	INV	LinkedIn	Link
126	17.06.21	INR	Twitter	Link
127	17.06.21	INR	LinkedIn	Link
128	17.06.21	INR	Facebook	Link
129	23.06.21	FBCD	LinkedIn	Link
130	25.06.21	INV	Twitter	Link
131	25.06.21	INV	LinkedIn	Link
132	30.06.21	INV	Twitter	Link
133	30.06.21	INV	LinkedIn	Link
134	30.06.21	FBCD	LinkedIn	Link
135	01.07.21	DTI	LinkedIn	Link
136	12.07.21	FBCD	LinkedIn	Link
137	27.08.21	FBCD	LinkedIn	Link
138	04.09.21	CHI	LinkedIn	Link
139	06.09.21	INR	Facebook	Link
140	06.09.21	INR	LinkedIn	Link
141	06.09.21	INR	Twitter	Link
142	14.09.21	DTI	LinkedIn	Link
143	16.09.21	DTI	LinkedIn	Link
144	16.09.21	TZ	LinkedIn	Link
145	20.09.21	FBCD	Twitter	Link
146	28.08.21	TL	LinkedIn	Link
147	28.09.21	GEA	LinkedIn	Link
148	28.09.21	GEA	Twitter	Link
149	28.09.21	GEA	Facebook	Link
150	15.10.21	FBCD	Facebook	Link
152	27.10.21	CHI	LinkedIn	Link

1.C. Target audience - All target groups (including general public)

Dissemination activity	Brochures and fact sheets Digital and printed format
Start month:	3
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of flyers/factsheets distributed
Target Value	6 roll-ups, 3.000 flyers, 1.400 factsheets
Lead Partner	Agro Business Park
Contributing Partners	All
Additional Information	All partners will be involved in distribution of flyers and factsheets

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

MATERIALS	TARGET VALUE	ORDERED/PRINTED
Roll-ups	6	4
Flyers/Brochures	3000	2200
Fact-sheets	1400	1600
Poster	2	7

1.D.1.Target audience - All target groups (including general public)

Dissemination activity	Publication in newspapers and journals At local, national, international level (Euractive.com; EuroNews, EUagenda) as well as relevant journals within food, rapeseed, olives, tomatoes, citrus
Start month:	1
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of articles
Target Value	>30 articles
Lead Partner	Agro Business Park
Contributing Partners	DTI, Bangor University, Vertech, Innovarum, Natac
Additional Information	All contributing partners will be responsible for at least five publications

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

NO.	WHEN*	WHO	WHERE / TOPIC	WHAT**	LINK
1	12.04.19	INV	Innovagri	Press Release	Link
2	12.04.19	INV	Profesionalagro.com	Article	Link
3	12.04.19	INV	Idi-A	Article	Link
4	03.05.19	INV	RICAgroalimentacion - Science, technology & engineering	Article	Link
5	03.05.19	ABP	Ingeniøren	Full-page article	Link

6	07.10.19	ABP	Klimanyt	Article	Link
7	20.12.19	JC	OLIMERCA-Encuentro de empresas del sector oleícola en la UJA	Article	Link
8	20.12.19	JC	Jaen University Digital Magazine-Encuentro con empresas del sector oleícola organizado por la OFIPI	Article	Link
9	02.03.20	INV	La Huerta Digital	Article	Link
10	23.04.20	INV	Biotech Spain	Article	Link
11	19.05.20	ABP	Viborg Stifts Folkeblad	Article	Link
12	25.05.20	ABP	Klimanyt	Article	Link
13	27.05.20	ABP	Ugeavisen Møldrup	Article	Only in print
14	01.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	Revista FyH	Article	Link
15	14.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	Biotech Spain	Article	Link
16	16.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	Balance, El Periòdic	Article	Link
17	16.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	Freshplaza.es	Article	Link
18	16.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	Murcia.com / Empresa	Article	Link
19	17.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	Freshplaza.com	Article	Link
20	17.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	InfoAgro.com	Article	Link
21	17.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	Zestfruit- European project tackles citrus waste	Article	Link
22	17.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	falmeria-Empresas españolas trabajan en vías para aprovechar los desechos de la industria de los cítricos	Article (PP.82)	Link
23	17.07.20	AC	Newsbiocom-Restos de los cítricos como combustible	Article	Link
24	17.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	Valencia Fruits newsletter	Article	Link
25	17.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	eComercioAgrario-Anecoop colabora en un proyecto europeo para dar valor a los desechos de cítricos	Article	Link
26	18.07.20	AC	Anecoop colabora en un proyecto europeo que busca vías para aprovechar los desechos de la industria de cítricos	Article	Link
27	19.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	El Agro Auténtico	Article	Link
28	21.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	www.agronoticias.es	Article	Link
29	23.07.20	NTC/INV/A C	Freshplaza.it	Article	Link
30	01.08.20	NTC/INV/A C	Anecoop collabore à un projet européen d'utilisation des déchets d'agrumes	Article	Link

32	19.10.20	BU	BBC Radio 4	Radio show/ podcast	Link
33	12.08.20	NTC/INV/A C	Eurofresh- The international distribution magazine for fresh produce & retail	Article	Link
34	13.08.20	NTC/INV/A C	Ein europäisches Projekt sucht nach Wegen zur Nutzung des Abfalls aus der Zitrusindustrie	Article	Link
35	22.09.20	ABP/INV	Uruganaderia.eu	Article	Link
36	25.08.20	NTC/INV/A C	España: Empresa colabora en un proyecto europeo para dar valor a los desechos de cítricos	Article	Link
37	01.09.20	NTC/INV/A C	Citricos de Chile - España: Empresas trabajan en vías para aprovechar los desechos de la industria de los cítricos Anecoop Sandía 2020	Article	Link
38	15.09.20	INV	Piensos a base de proteínas vegetales para mascotas	Article	Link
39	30.09.20	BU	S4C daily news for youngsters (BBC)	Segment	Link
40	30.09.20	BU	Western Mail	Article	Link
41	01.10.20	BU	The Daily Post (Paper edition)	Article	Only in print
42	07.10.20	DTI	www.gts-net.dk	Article	Link
43	07.10.20	BU	Bangor & Anglesley Mail (paper edition)	Article	Only in print
44	15.10.21	FBCD	Ritzau	Press release	Link

1.E. Target audience - All target groups (including general public)

Dissemination activity	Final event
	Available also in streaming to reach the broadest possible audience
Start month:	36
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of participant and new connections
Target Value	100 participants, and connections
Lead Partner	Agro Business Park
Contributing Partners	DTI, Innovarum, InnoRenew, Bangor University
Additional Information	ABP/DTI (North), Innovarum (South), InnoRenew (East) and Bangor University (West) will be responsible for local promotion of "final event"

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

EVENT	WHO	WHEN/WHERE
Final Event	FBCD/ DTI	14-10-21 (M42) at Danish Technological Institute in Copenhagen (75 participants)

1.F. Target audience - All target groups (including general public)

Dissemination activity	EC Dissemination routes
	The consortium partners will ensure that the excellent dissemination tools provided by the EC for dissemination to European citizens, industry and the scientific community will be utilised in the project. Details of the project will be made available for articles to be included in European electronic and paper publications such as research*eu.
Start month:	6
Indicator to measure the impact	Visibility on EU websites
Target Value	Presence of a project page
Lead Partner	Agro Business Park
Contributing Partners	DTI

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

WHERE	LINK
Official Homepage	Link
Bio-Based Industries	Link
CORDIS	Link
Welsh Government services and information	Link
European Policies Research Centre Delft	Link

2.A. Target audience - Research and scientific community

Dissemination activity	Publication in Journals
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The research organisations and universities in the consortium will author scientific articles describing the scientific and technical achievements of the project for publication in peer-reviewed journals, for example: International Journal of Recycling of Organic Waste in Agriculture; Waste and Biomass Valorisation; Biochemical Engineering Journal; Biotechnology and Engineering; Industrial Crops and Products; Biorefinery; Bioresources; Journal of renewable materials.

When possible, the research organisations will preferably use “gold” (open access) or green” (self-archiving) access for depositing peer reviewed research and final manuscripts arising from their activities in the Pro-Enrich project, in line with the EC’s Open Access Pilot initiative and allowing the scientific community greater access to the knowledge generated in the project.

Start month:	Results obtained
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of papers published
Target Value	>5 papers published
Lead Partner	Bangor University
Contributing Partners	DTI, InnoRenew

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT				
PUBLICATION NO.	WHEN	WHO	WHERE	Link
1	19.10.19	BU	Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies	Link
2	22.10.20	INR	Journal of Natural Products	Link
3	23.10.21	BU/INR /GEA	Molecules	Link
4	01.08.21	INR/GEA /BU	Food and Bioproducts Processing	Pending
5	25.10.21	INR/DTI	Plants	Pending
6	27.10.21	INR	Molecules	Pending
7	02.11.21	BU/INR	Bioresources Technology	In preparation

2.B. Target audience - Research and scientific community

Dissemination activity	Web 2.0 tools ResearchGate, SlideShare, YouTube, LinkedIn
Start month:	4
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of posts and visualisations
Target Value	>60 posts, 1500 visualisations
Lead Partner	Agro Business Park
Contributing Partners	DTI, Innovarum, InnoRenew All companies contributing when relevant

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

POST NO.	WHEN	WHO	WHERE	LINK
1	01.05.18	INV	Website	Link
2	03.05.18	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
3	03.05.18	INR	Facebook	Link
4	03.05.18	INR	Facebook	Link
5	03.05.18	INR	Twitter	Link
6	28.05.18	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
7	05.07.18	BU	Twitter	Link
8	06.07.18	INV	Website	Link
9	20.07.18	BU	Twitter	Link
10	03.09.18	INR	LinkedIn	Link
11	03.09.18	INR	Twitter	Link
12	03.09.18	INR	Facebook	Link
13	27.09.18	INV	Twitter	Link
14	15.10.18	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
15	16.10.18	INV	Twitter	Link
16	25.10.18	BU	Twitter	Link
17	25.10.18	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
18	29.10.18	INR	Facebook	Link
19	29.10.18	INR	Twitter	Link
20	29.10.18	INR	LinkedIn	Link
21	14.11.18	INV	Twitter	Link
22	15.11.18	INV	Twitter	Link
23	19.11.18	INR	Facebook	Link
24	19.11.18	INR	Twitter	Link
25	26.11.18	INV	Website	Link
26	29.11.18	INV	LinkedIn	Link
27	19.11.18	INR	LinkedIn	Link
28	10.01.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link
29	15.01.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
30	17.01.19	BU	Twitter	Link
31	22.01.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link
32	31.01.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link
33	04.02.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link

34	11.02.19	INV	Twitter & LinkedIn	Link
35	14.02.19	VER	Facebook	Link
36	14.02.19	VER	Linkedin	Link
37	01.03.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
38	11.03.19	INV	Twitter	Link
39	11.03.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
40	15.03.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
41	20.03.19	INV	Twitter	Link
42	25.03.19	INV	Twitter	Link
43	25.03.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
44	27.03.19	BU	Twitter	Link
45	01.04.19	GEA	LinkedIn	Link
46	02.04.19	INV	Twitter	Link
47	02.04.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
48	10.04.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
49	12.04.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
50	14.07.19	BU	Twitter	Link
51	15.04.19	INV	Twitter	Link
52	15.04.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
53	23.04.19	INV	LinkedIn	Link
54	24.05.19	BU	Twitter	Link
55	11.06.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
56	15.06.19	VER	LinkedIn	Link
57	20.06.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
58	07.08.19	BU	Youtube	Link
59	28.08.19	INR	Twitter	Link
60	03.09.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
61	06.09.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
62	06.09.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
63	16.09.19	BU	Twitter	Link
64	12.09.19	BU	Twitter	Link
65	12.09.19	BU	Twitter	Link
66	01.10.19	BU	Twitter	Link
67	19.11.19	NAT	LinkedIn	Link
68	20.11.19	VER	LinkedIn	Link
69	21.11.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
70	05.12.19	ABP	LinkedIn	Link
71	20.12.19	DTI	LinkedIn	Link
72	14.01.20	INV	Twitter	Link
73	14.01.20	INV	LinkedIn	Link
74	12.02.20	BU	Twitter	Link
75	14.02.20	INV	LinkedIn	Link
76	03.03.20	INV	Twitter	Link
77	03.03.20	INV	LinkedIn	Link
78	14.04.20	INV	Twitter	Link
79	14.04.20	INV	LinkedIn	Link
80	17.4.20	BU	Twitter	Link
81	21.04.20	INV	Twitter	Link

82	21.04.20	INV	LinkedIN	Link
83	24.04.20	NTC	LinkedIN	Link
84	23.04.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
85	23.04.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
86	24.04.20	NTC	LinkedIN	Link
87	24.04.20	NTC	LinkedIN	Link
88	29.04.20	ABP	LinkedIN	Link
89	29.04.20	ABP	LinkedIN	Link
90	30.04.20	INR	LinkedIN	Link
91	30.04.20	INR	Twitter	Link
92	30.04.20	INR	Facebook	Link
93	25.05.20	ABP	LinkedIN	Link
94	25.05.20	ABP	Facebook	Link
95	04.06.20	INV	Twitter	Link
96	02.07.20	INV	Twitter	Link
97	14.07.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
98	21.07.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
99	21.08.20	BU	Twitter	Link
100	03.09.20	INV	Twitter	Link
101	03.09.20	NTC	Twitter	Link
102	07.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
103	08.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
104	15.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
105	19.10.20	BU	Twitter	Link
106	21.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
107	27.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
108	29.10.20	INV	Twitter	Link
109	06.11.20	INV	Twitter	Link
110	10.11.20	GEA	LinkedIN	Link
111	10.11.20	GEA	LinkedIN	Link
112	10.11.20	GEA	Facebook	Link
113	10.11.20	GEA	Facebook	Link
114	10.11.20	GEA	Twitter	Link
115	24.11.20	FBCD	LinkedIN	Link
		Welch		
		Government		
116	24.02.21	Office, Brussels	Twitter	Link
117	08.03.21	Natac	LinkedIn	Link
118	10.04.21	DTI	LinkedIN	Link
119	01.03.21	CHI	LinkedIn	Link
120	17.05.21	INV	LinkedIN	Link
121	18.05.21	CHI	LinkedIN	Link
122	15.06.21	FBCD	LinkedIN	Link
123	15.06.21	FBCD	LinkedIn	Link
124	16.06.21	INV	Twitter	Link
125	16.06.21	INV	LinkedIn	Link
126	17.06.21	INR	Twitter	Link
127	17.06.21	INR	LinkedIn	Link

128	17.06.21	INR	Facebook	Link
129	23.06.21	FBCD	LinkedIN	Link
130	25.06.21	INV	Twitter	Link
131	25.06.21	INV	Linkedin	Link
132	30.06.21	INV	Twitter	Link
133	30.06.21	INV	Linkedin	Link
134	30.06.21	FBCD	Linkedin	Link
135	01.07.21	DTI	Linkedin	Link
136	12.07.21	FBCD	Linkedin	Link
137	27.08.21	FBCD	Linkedin	Link
138	04.09.21	CHI	LinkedIn	Link
139	06.09.21	INR	Facebook	Link
140	06.09.21	INR	LinkedIN	Link
141	06.09.21	INR	Twitter	Link
142	14.09.21	DTI	LinkedIN	Link
143	16.09.21	DTI	LinkedIN	Link
144	16.09.21	TZ	LinkedIN	Link
145	20.09.21	FBCD	Twitter	Link
146	28.08.21	TL	LinkedIN	Link
147	28.09.21	GEA	LinkedIN	Link
148	28.09.21	GEA	Twitter	Link
149	28.09.21	GEA	Facebook	Link
150	15.10.21	FBCD	Facebook	Link
152	27.10.21	CHI	LinkedIN	Link

2.C. Target audience - Research and scientific community

Dissemination activity	Lectures, webinars Use of project and its results in lectures and as a subject for universities
Start month:	12
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of lectures
Target Value	At least 4 lectures
Lead Partner	Bangor University
Contributing Partners	DTI, InnoRenew, Bangor University

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

LECTURE NO.	WHEN	WHO	WHERE	WHAT
1	05.10.18	BU	Bangor University	Presentation to Bangor University research staff- overview of the Pro-Enrich project

2	05.05.19	INR	Brno, Czech Republic, Department of Wood Science, Faculty of Forestry and Wood Technology	Invited Lecture
3	10.04.19	BU	Machynlleth, Wales	Invited Lecture to 60 MSc students: Module EV7103- Ecosystem services, land-use, water and waste management (Materials Resources and Waste), Centre for Alternative Technology. Lecture content included case studies on the valorisation of food waste/ processing residues, including Pro-Enrich
4	04.09.19	INR	Zagreb, Croatia	Invited lecture at the Faculty of Forestry at the University of Zagreb
5	31.10.19	INR	Madison, WI, USA	Invited lecture at the Forest Products Laboratory
6	13.02.20	INR	Kuchl, Austria	Invited lecture at the Salzburg University of Applied Sciences, Kuchl Fachhochschule location
7	17.02.20	INR	Eberswalde, Germany	Invited lecture at the Eberswalde University for Sustainable development
8	18.02.20	INR	Braunschweig, Germany	Invited lecture at the Technical University of Braunschweig

2.D.1.Target audience - Research and scientific community

Dissemination activity	Participation in broad events
	Open day at the Universities, Researchers' Nights (each year in September), and Knowledge Open Festivals
Start month:	9
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of events attended
Target Value	At least 10 events attended
Lead Partner	DTI
Contributing Partners	Bangor University, Innovarum, Agro Business Park,

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT				
EVENT NO.	WHEN*	WHO	WHERE	WHAT
1	27.09.18	DTI	Sakskøbing, Denmark	Danish Bio-Economy Conference
2	14.01.19	BU	Shrewsbury, England Bangor	Attended the Natural Resources Wales, State of Natural Resources Report (SONARR) workshop. This was to assist in developing KPIs that will be used to determine the impact of the Circular Economy in Wales
3	20.03.19	DTI	Taastrup, Denmark	Open House at the Danish Technological Institute talk on: 'Added-value side-streams from marine and agricultural residues on pilot scale - advancing demonstration and commercialisation'.
4	25-27.06.19	ABP	Foulum, Denmark	Circular Bioeconomy Days, Foulum Denmark
5	06.09.19	ABP	Aarhus, Denmark	Food Festival, Aarhus, Denmark
6	04.07.19	BU	Cardiff, UK	Welsh Gov H2020 Annual Event
7	23.09.19	DTI	Sakskøbing, Denmark	Danish Bio-Economy Conference
8	23.10.20	FBCD	Aarhus, Denmark	Aarhus University iNANO autumn school
9	18.11.20	DTI	Online	RTO Innovation Summit
10	26.11.20	FBCD	Online	The future of food - Unlocking the benefits of Scotland's circular economy
11	10.11.20	INV	Madrid, Spain	Madrid Science Week
13	02.03.21	BU	Webinar	Pro-Enrich featured as a case in webinar "The Importance of the EU Regions in Welsh Innovation" (21:30)

2.E.1. Target audience - Research and scientific community

Dissemination activity	Exhibitions and conferences The research partners will deliver presentations at conference describing their activities and results obtained during the project to target the scientific and technical communities, for example: at major international conferences such as International Consultative Group for Research on Rapeseed. 15th GCIRC Rapeseed Congress, Berlin, June 16-20, 2019. XV International Symposium on Processing Tomato - XIII World Processing Tomato Congress. Location, Athens (Greece) June 11, 2018.
Start month:	6
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of events attended
Target Value	At least 15 events attended
Lead Partner	DTI
Contributing Partners	Bangor University, InnoRenew All companies potentially contributing to Exhibition

AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

EXHIBITION/ CONFERENCE NO.	WHEN*	WHO	WHERE	WHAT
1	25.04.2018	DTI	Taastrup, Denmark	Forskningens Døgn
2	27.09.18	DTI	Sakskøbing, Denmark	Danish Bio-Economy Conference
3	14.01.19	BU	Shrewsbury, England Bangor	Attended the Natural Resources Wales, State of Natural Resources Report (SONARR) workshop. This was to assist in developing KPIs that will be used to determine the impact of the Circular Economy in Wales.
4	20.03.19	DTI	Taastrup, Denmark	Open House at the Danish Technological Institute talk on: 'Added-value side-streams from marine and agricultural residues on pilot scale - advancing demonstration and commercialisation'.
5	25-27.06.19	ABP	Foulum, Denmark	Circular Bioeconomy Days, Foulum Denmark
6	06.09.19	ABP	Aarhus, Denmark	Food Festival, Aarhus, Denmark
7	04.07.19	BU	Cardiff, UK	Welsh Gov H2020 Annual Event
8	23.09.19	DTI, ABP	Sakskøbing, Denmark	Danish Bio-Economy Conference

9	28.05.20	INV, ABP, DTI	Online	eWorkshop on Upcycled Proteins
10	18.11.20	DTI	Virtual exhibition	RTO Innovation summit 2020
11	19 & 26.11.20	FBCD	Virtual event	The Future of Food - Zero Waste Scotland. Presented the Pro-Enrich project on day 2.
12	10-11. 02.21	FBCD	Online	Bringing Value to Agrobiomass - Supporting project and matchmaking profile on webpage
13	06.03.21	INR	Flagstaff, AZ, USA	Abstract submitted for Value from Wood Resources through Innovation conference, International Society for Wood Science & technology. To be held in August 2021.
14	11.05.21	CHIMAR	Online	Exhibitor at WBPI (Wood-Based Panels Industry) Beyond Covid-19 online Conference & Fair
15	28.05.20	INV, ABP,	Online	eWorkshop on Upcycled Proteins
16	13-15. 07.21	INR DTI		International conference of polyphenols - ICP2021.

3.A.1. Target audience - Industries

Dissemination activity

Participation at conferences, seminars, trade shows, exhibitions, Papers, posters and ppt presentation, Face-to-face meetings

Preliminary list:

FEICA European Adhesive & Sealant Conference and EXPO;
 EURAD – European conference on Adhesion and Adhesive;
 Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy Conference; Feed Additives;
 Bio-Based Live Europe (BBI JU is associate sponsor in 2017);
 European Biomass Conference;
 THE LARGEST FOOD TRADE FAIR IN THE NORDIC COUNTRIES. Denmark, Herning Foodexpo
 ANUGA FOOD TECH, Köln
 International Conference on Renewable Resources & Biorefineries, RRB 14, Ghent 30. May-1. June 2018
 ANUGA FOOD FAIR, Cologne, October 2019, Germany;
 Ligna fair, Hannover, May 2019;
 Nutrifair, Fredericia, Denmark.
 Protein summit, October 2018, Reims, France.
 Food tech 2018, Barcelona, Spain.

Food Ingredients Europe, Paris 2019
 Vitafoods, May 2018, Geneva, Switzerland
 ALIBETOPIAS, Spain (www.alibetopias.es).
 Fruit logistica (Berlin) (2018,2019,2020)
 Fruti Attraction (Madrid) (2018,2019,2020)
 Alimentaria (Barcelona) (2018,2019,2020)

Start month: 3
 Indicator to measure the impact: No. of events attended and presentation/ speeches
 Target Value: At least 20 events attended
 Lead Partner: DTI
 Contributing Partners: All
 Additional Information: List will be updated on a yearly basis

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT				
EVENT NO.	WHEN*	WHO	WHERE	WHAT
1	27.09.18	DTI	Sakskøbing, Denmark	Presentation at Danish Bioeconomy Conference 2018 (Dansk Bioøkonomi Konference)
2	27.09.18	INV	Torino, Italy	Presentation at International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy (IFIB)
3	16.10.18	INV	Cordoba, Spain	Presentation at FIMART – Fair for Smart Rural Innovation
4	18.10.18	AC	Madrid, Spain	Presentation at ALIBETOPIAS
5	25.10.18	ABP	Copenhagen, Denmark	Presentation at The European Investment Bank Copenhagen conference on the circular economy,
6	06.11.18	ABP	Randers, Denmark	Presentation at Network for polymers
7	18.12.18	ABP	Aarhus, Denmark	Presentation for and meeting with The Danish Agriculture & Food Council
8	29.01.19	BU	Bangor, Wales	Presentation of Pro-Enrich at Sustainable Packaging Workshop
9	20.02.19	DTI/ABP	Brussels, Belgium	Presentation at Bio-Based Industries Consortium - Matchmaking Event 2019

10	28.02.19	ABP	Hedensted, Denmark	Presentation for the "Innovation network for Bioresources" steering group
11	6-9.05.19	INV	Milano, Italy	Booth at Seeds & Chips 2019
12	02.04.19	ABP	Lyngby, Denmark	Presentation at the national BBI info day at Haldor Topsøe
13	7-9.05.2019	NTC	Geneva, Switzerland	Vitafoods Europe
14	27-31.05.19	CHM	Hannover, Germany	LIGNA FAIR 2019
15	21.05.19	ABP	Sorø, Denmark	Poster presentation at the international conference "plant proteins in foods and diets"
16	27.05.19	ABP+DTI+(GEA)	Foulum, Denmark	Poster presentation (ABP) and PPT presentation (DTI) at "Circular Bioeconomy Days"
17	30.10.19	T&L	Deeside, wales, UK	NORTH WALES BUSINESS EXHIBITION 2019
17	25.09.19	ABP+DTI+(GEA)	Sakskøbing, Denmark	Danish Bioeconomy Conference 2019 (Dansk Bioøkonomi Konference) - Roll-up and distribution of brochure and fact-sheet + showing Rape seed protein concentrate
18	03.12.19	ABP/ INV	Brussels, Belgium	BBI JU - Projects Day. Pro-Enrich was presented at exhibition booth 7B with roll-up, brochure and fact-sheet.
19	04.12.19	ABP+Innovarum	Brussels, Belgium	BBI JU Stakeholder Forum. Pro-Enrich was presented at exhibition booth 7B with roll-up, brochure and fact-sheet.
20	20.12.19	JC	Jaen, Spain	Oral presentation of ProEnrich Project as an experience of I+D+i of a company of the olive sector. The event was promoted by the

				International Projects Office of the University of Jaen.
21	21/22. 01.20	ABP + Emme- lev	Fredericia, Denmark	NutriFair exhibitions and tradeshow. Pro-Enrich was presented at the ABP booth D-3208.
22	03.02.20	ABP	Århus, Denmark	Presentation at the national BBI info day at the Danish Technological Institute
23	09.10.20	INV	Online	EFIB 2020: Poster presentation
25	15.04.21	DTI/FBCD	Online	Presentation at New plant- based ingredients - New cooperation Protein Industries Canada - Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
26	28.04.21	INV	Online	EUBCE 2021: poster presentation of the Pro- Enrich project (screenshots sent, ask if more needed)
27	17.05.21	INV	Online	Murcia Food 2021: poster presentation of the Pro- Enrich project

3.B.1.Target audience - Research and scientific community

Dissemination activity	Articles and features in industrial journals and magazines
	In order to stimulate interest in the take up and dissemination of the new Pro-Enrich processing methods, product range and subsequent applications, the project's industrial partners will produce articles publication in trade journals relevant to developments in the project.
Start month:	3
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of articles published
Target Value	>10 articles
Lead Partner	InnoRenew
Contributing Partners	Bangor University, DTI
Additional Information	In collaboration with companies GEA, Vertech, Natac

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT						
NO.	WHEN*	WHO	WHERE	WHAT	Link	
1	28.08.19	INR	InnoRenew Website	On-line article with an interview of Matthew Schwarzkopf targeting the general public and letting them know about the Pro-Enrich project	Link	
2	04.06.19	INR	Olive Oil Times	On-line article with an interview of Matthew Schwarzkopf, Innorenew and a presentation of the Pro-Enrich project	Link	
3	12.09.19	BU	New Food	Title of on-line article "Producing protein from food waste"	Link	
4	16.12.19	GEA	GEA newsletter	Valorizing food production waste through functional ingredients extraction	Link	
5	01.01.20	BU	Advanced Wales	Presentation of Pro-Enrich project	Link	
6	17.07.20	NTC/ INV/ AC	AGF Nederland - News platform for the Dutch and Belgian fruit and vegetable trade	Article	Link	
7	20.07.20	NTC/ INV/ AC	Fruitnet.com	Article	Link	
8	22.07.20	NTC/ INV/ AC	Biotech Spain	Article	Link	
9	01.08.20	INV	Mundo del Agronomo. No. 46, pp 15, 16, 17	Article	Link	
10	19.08.20	NTC/ INV/ AC	Fruchthandel Online	Article	Link	
11	21.08.20	BU	Food Manufacture magazine	Upcycling foodwaste into new proteins and ingredients	Link	

3.C. Target audience - Research and scientific community

Dissemination activity	Promotion through professional organisations The consortium partners will use the following profession bodies (and their “trade“ publications), networks, trade associations and European Technology Platforms (ETP) as a means to disseminate the results and benefits of the Pro-Enrich project throughout the EU, as well as the BBI platform.
Start month:	1
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of meetings attended, No. of contacts gained
Target Value	>10meetings, >150 contacts
Lead Partner	DTI
Contributing Partners	Agro Business Park, Innovarum
Additional Information	ABP will assist DTI in Northern Europe and Innovarum will assist in Southern part of Europe

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT				
MEETING NO.	WHEN	WHO	WHERE	WHAT
1	31.08.18	DTI	Taastrup, Denmark	Danish Environment Technology Associations (DETA): Presentation of Pro-Enrich and tour of pilot plant
2	20.02.19	ABP/DTI	Brussels, Denmark	BIC matchmaking event 2019
3	28.02.19	DTI	Taastrup, Denmark	Nordic RTOs - Towards a Nordic and Baltic Sea Region testbed infrastructure (GTS Denmark, RISE Sweden, VTT Finland and SINTEF and RISE Norway)
4	26.03.19	DTI/ABP	Copenhagen, Denmark	The National Bioeconomy Panel - Workshop on biopolymers
5	02.09.19	DTI	Copenhagen, Denmark	Danish Environment Technology Associations (DETA): Partnership on Sustainable Biorefining, Meeting with Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark
6	27.02.20	DTI	Copenhagen, Denmark	Bioplastics Conference, IDA polymer
7	13.02.20	ABP/DTI/NATAC	Brussels, Denmark	BIC matchmaking event 2020
8	22/23.04.20	ABP/INV/DTI	Online	BBI JU Info Day 2020
8	12.05.20	INV	Online	BBI JU Info Day 2020

9	17.09.20	BU	Online	Article in the Welsh Governments H2020 newsletter
10	27.09.21	FBCD	Copenhagen, Denmark	Pro-Enrich mentioned in meeting about improvement of framework conditions for biosolutions in Denmark (to five ministries, major industry associations, knowledge institutions, and more).

CONTACT NO.	WHEN	WHO	WHERE	WHAT
1	31.08.18	Lars Storm Pedersen, Haldor Topsoe	Taastrup, Denmark	C5 and C6 uses for new applications
2	31.08.18	Jacob Kragh Andersen, Envidan	Taastrup, Denmark	Solutions for the water and wastewater
3	31.08.18	Erik Bundgaard, Kruger	Taastrup, Denmark	Water treatment technologies
4	31.08.18	Theis Nikolaj Gadegaard, Kruger	Taastrup, Denmark	Water treatment technologies
5	31.08.18	Niels Henriksen, Orsted	Taastrup, Denmark	Green energy solutions
6	31.08.18	Erik C. Wormslev, Niras	Taastrup, Denmark	Consultant company on sustainable solutions
7	31.08.18	Jesper Lund Larsen, 3F	Taastrup, Denmark	Workers association
8	31.08.18	Kathrine Dose Stenild, Novozymes	Taastrup, Denmark	Enzyme provider
9	31.08.18	Ole Bandsholm Sørensen, KMC	Taastrup, Denmark	Potato processing and cascading resource use
10	31.08.18	Espen Tind-Nordberg, Danish EPA	Taastrup, Denmark	Legislation
11	31.08.18	Thyge Nygaard, The Danish Society for Nature Conservation	Taastrup, Denmark	Nature conservation and environmental organisation in Denmark
12	31.08.18	Rikke Lundsgaard, The Danish Society for Nature Conservation	Taastrup, Denmark	Nature conservation and environmental organisation in Denmark
13	31.08.18	Uffe Jørgensen, University of Aarhus	Taastrup, Denmark	Researcher on biorefining
14	31.08.18	Claus Felby, University of Copenhagen	Taastrup, Denmark	Researcher on biorefining
15	31.08.18	Nana Winkler, Danish Waste Association	Taastrup, Denmark	political interest organisation consisting of municipal waste entities

16	31.08.18	Thomas Holst, Danish agriculture and food council	Taastrup, Denmark	Represents the farming and food industry of Denmark including companies, trade and farmers' associations
17	31.08.18	John P Jensen, NordZucker	Taastrup, Denmark	Cascading use of sugar beets
18	31.08.18	Mette Boye, Danish Environment Technology Associations	Taastrup, Denmark	The is to put advanced solutions to global environmental challenges on the top of the political agenda nationally, in the EU and internationally
19	01.01.19	Annette Bruhn, University of Aarhus	Taastrup, Denmark	Researcher on biorefining
20	28.02.19	Elis Benediktsson, Nordic Innovation	Taastrup, Denmark	Working to promote cross-border trade and innovation
21	26.03.19	Gitte Haar, Krasilnikoff	Copenhagen, Denmark	Consultant company on sustainable solutions
22	26.03.19	Birgit Bonefeld, Selfe employed	Copenhagen, Denmark	Material designer
23	02.09.19	Morten Ambye-Jensen, Foulum, AU	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	Biorefining pilot and demoplant
24	02.09.19	Kira Kalsen Nissen, Landbrugsstyrelsen	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	Regulatory affairs
25	02.09.19	Milica Folic, Haldor Topsøe	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	C5 and C6 uses for new applications
26	02.09.19	Thomas Holst, Landbrug & Fødevarer	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	Resource utilization
27	02.09.19	Rikke Lundsgaard, Denmakrs Naturfredningsforening	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark,	Environmental protection

28	02.09.19	Henning Jørgensen, University of Copenhagen, DK	Copenhagen, Denmark Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	Researcher on biorefining
29	02.09.19	Jeppe Røn Hartmann, Drivkraft Danmark	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	Transport and logistics
30	02.09.19	Kristen Kristensen, Shell	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	Energy provider and refining
31	02.09.19	Kasper Bruun Knudsen, Novozymes	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	Enzyme provider
32	02.09.19	Mathias Greve-Poulsen, KMC	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	New uses of sidestreams
33	02.09.19	Anne Sophie Vinther Hansen, Maersk	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	Transport and logistics
34	02.09.19	Per Dunkelskov Thomsen, Daka	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	New uses of sidestreams
35	02.09.19	Jan-Michael Blum, Envidan	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark	Energy, water and environment

36	19.02.20	Analia Gottig, Bridge2Food	Microsoft teams	Potential cooperation on events in Pro-Enrich and Plenitude projects
37	09.01.20	Ole Kaae Hansen	OK Biotech	Speak about opportunities and status in alternative proteins
38	13.02.20	Dragica Marinic, Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Štajerska	Brussels, Belgium	BIC matchmaking event 2020
39	13.02.20	Zsófia Kádár, Bio-Base Europe Pilot Plant	Brussels, Belgium	BIC matchmaking event 2020
40	13.02.20	Sofie Lodens, Bio-Base Europe Pilot Plant	Brussels, Belgium	BIC matchmaking event 2020
41	13.02.20	Johan VAN DER VEEN, SUSPACC	Brussels, Belgium	BIC matchmaking event 2020
42	13.02.20	Doga Arslan, KU Leuven	Brussels, Belgium	BIC matchmaking event 2020
43	13.02.20	Stephanie Roosa: Mareria Nova, Belgium	Brussels, Belgium	Development and prototype production of biofibre materials
44	13.02.20	Ioannis Fallas, Clube, Greece	Brussels, Belgium	Potential of establishing a generic biorefining pilot plant in Greece
45	13.02.20	Ferran Ferrer, Aimplas, Spain	Brussels, Belgium	development, upscaling and validation of processes for food grade pilot scale biorefinery production of functional components
46	13.02.20	Gloria de la Viña Nieto, CTA, Spain	Brussels, Belgium	Exploitation and communication
47	13.02.20	Marcel van Berkel, Bio based Delta	Brussels, Belgium	development, upscaling and validation of processes for biorefinery hydrolysis, fractionation and separation of selected biomass for production of functional components
48	13.02.20	Paul Konst, TNO, The Netherlands	Brussels, Belgium	biorefinery hydrolysis, fractionation and separation of selected biomass for production of functional components
49	13.02.20	Andrzej Bialowiec, Wroclow University, Poland	Brussels, Belgium	Sugar utilization

50	13.02.20	Lara Valentin, Funditec, Spain	Brussels, Belgium	development, upscaling and validation of processes for food grade pilot scale biorefinery production of functional components
51	13.02.20	Tadeusz Peczek, Pro Civis, Poland	Brussels, Belgium	Extraction of bioactive compounds
52	13.02.20	Manuela Cano Galey, Andaltec, Spain	Brussels, Belgium	knowledge on the processability
53	27.02.20	Daniela Bach, Rockfon/IDA Polymer	Copenhagen, Denmark	Materials specialist (contact established during planning of the event)
54	27.02.20	Pia Dahlin, BASF/Nordic Bioplastic	Copenhagen, Denmark	Polymer specialist, representative for the association of Nordic Bioplastics (contact established during planning of the event)
55	27.02.20	Hans Friedsam, Nord Emballage/Nordic Bioplastic	Copenhagen, Denmark	Polymer specialist, representative for the association of Nordic Bioplastics (contact established during planning of the event)
56	27.02.20	Rasmus Grusgaard, The Danish Plastics Federation	Copenhagen, Denmark	Trade association for plastics converting companies in Denmark and their suppliers (contact established during planning of the event)
57	27.02.20	Kevin Le Dez, ARRDHOR - CRITT Horticole	Copenhagen, Denmark	Development of biobased pigments
58	27.02.20	Clara Pierrou, RenFuel	Copenhagen, Denmark	Lignin Bio oils
59	27.02.20	Camilla, Østervang Gård	Copenhagen, Denmark	SME with brewery and juice production
60	27.02.20	Eike Langenberg, FKUR Polymers	Copenhagen, Denmark	Producer of biobased polymers
61	27.02.20	Martin Lidstrand, Trifilon	Copenhagen, Denmark	Biobased composites for injection moulding
62	27.02.20	Bo Madsen, DTU	Copenhagen, Denmark	Materials specialist, research on (biobased) composites
63	27.02.20	Jesper Bøgelund, Novo Nordisk	Copenhagen, Denmark	materials specialist, biobased materials for medico devices

64	27.02.20	Marianne Strange, Grundfos	Copenhagen, Denmark	materials specialist, pumping systems
65	22.04.20	Christophe Luguel, IAR, France	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
66	22.04.20	Emil Lezak, Iznab Spolka Z Ograniczona Odpowiedzialnoscia, Poland	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
67	22.04.20	Anne Delille, Centre for Process Innovation, UK	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
68	22.04.20	Alexandros Chatgialiloglu, Remembrane Srl, Italy	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
69	22.04.20	Stefania Baldassarre, CiaoTech (PNO Group), Italy	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
70	22.04.20	Peter Skagerlund, pSk earth adaption AB, Sweden	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
71	22.04.20	Seija Aalto, Center of Expertise Biobased Economy, The Netherlands	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
72	22.04.20	Sam Davis, Insight Media, UK	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
73	22.04.20	Lukas Paltanavicius, Wageningen University, The Netherlands	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
74	22.04.20	Rebeca Figueroa, CETIM Technological Center, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
75	22.04.20	Jesus Escudero, INIA, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
76	22.04.20	Bill Morrissey, Glanbia Ingredients, Ireland	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
77	22.04.20	Johan Belfrage, IBioIC, UK	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
78	22.04.20	Maria Lopez, Idener, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
79	22.04.20	Josef Sperl, Chemie-Cluster Bayern, Germany	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
80	22.04.20	Luiz Elizondo, NEIKER, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
81	22.04.20	Doga Arslan, KU Leuven	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
82	22.04.20	Oliver Bennett, Iconic Innovation, UK	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020

83	22.04.20	Patricia Cinelli, INSTM, Italy	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
84	22.04.20	Yorick Debeus, Leyton, Belgium	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
85	22.04.20	Brecht Vanlerberghe, VITO, Belgium	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
86	22.04.20	Jamen Leahy, University of Limerick, Ireland	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
87	22.04.20	Filippo Martinelli, Irish Bioeconomy Foundation, Ireland	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
88	22.04.20	Manuela Cano Galey, Andaltec, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
89	22.04.20	Olle Stenberg, Marine Feed, Sweden	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
90	22.04.20	Nóra Hatvani, Bay Zoltan Nonprofit Ltd. For Applied Research, Hungary	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
91	22.04.20	David Calvo Hernando, Universidad de Burgos, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
92	22.04.20	María DÍAZ NAVARRO, Cluster FOOD+i, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
93	22.04.20	José Manuel Ramos Fernández, AITEX Textiles research institute, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
94	22.04.20	Julie Maguire, Bantry Marine Research Station, Ireland	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
95	22.04.20	Andrea Cattaruzza, ANDCAT LTD, UK	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
96	22.04.20	Birgitte Holt Andersen, Applied Economics, Denmark	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
97	22.04.20	Marie Monestier, CTP - Centre Technique du Papier, France	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
98	22.04.20	Ivona Miketa, Bio-mi, Croatia	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
99	22.04.20	Mark Zver, Acies Bio D.O.O., Slovenia	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
100	22.04.20	Mathieu Schwander, CLEPA (European association of automotive suppliers), Belgium	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020

101	22.04.20	Sophie Mailley, CEA Tech, France	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
102	23.04.20	Ettore Musacchi, ETRA, Belgium	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
103	23.04.20	Christopher Whiteoak, University of Alcalá, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
104	23.04.20	Momme Velmede, pharmABC, Germany	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
105	23.04.20	Maria Jose Suarez, GAIKER-IK4, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
106	23.04.20	Fabiana Fantinel, Innoexc GMBH, Switzerland	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
107	23.04.20	Aykut Sancakli, KCL R&D Center, Turkey	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
108	23.04.20	Julia A. Gutierrez, University of Oviedo, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
109	23.04.20	Yelizaveta Chernysh, Sumy State University, Ukraine	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
110	23.04.20	Iker Ayerbe, FEUGA Universidad Gallega, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
111	23.04.20	Evelina Castellana, Lomartov SL, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
112	23.04.20	Adela Popa, University of Cadiz, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
113	23.04.20	Alexios Pagkozidis, Hypertech, Greece	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
114	23.04.20	Marta E. G. Mosquera, University of Alcalá, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
115	23.04.20	Mustafa Ersoz, Selcuk University, Turkey	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
116	23.04.20	Luka Dobrovic, Particula Group, Croatia	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
117	23.04.20	Carlos Moyano, ITENE Packaging Transport and Logistics research, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
118	23.04.20	Mohamed Gargouri, INSAT, Tunisia	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
119	23.04.20	Richard Moll, Clariant, Germany	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
120	23.04.20	Robert WUDARCZYK, RWENERGIA, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020

121	23.04.20	Monse Garabato, BIOGA, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
122	23.04.20	Ioannis Fallas, Cluster of Bioeconomy and Environment of Western Macedonia, Greece	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
123	23.04.20	Teija Laitinen, CLIC Innovation Ltd Finland	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
124	23.04.20	Silvia Giovanna AVATANEO, Crf Scpa, Italy	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
125	23.04.20	Goizeder Barberena, CENER - National Renewable Energy Center, Spain	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
126	23.04.20	Veronika Reinberg, Alchemia-Nova, Austria	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
127	23.04.20	Maurizio Bettiga, EviKrets Biobased Processes Consultants, Sweden	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
128	23.04.20	Ilaria Re, Consorzio Italbiotec, Italy	Online	BBI JU Info day 2020
129	12.05.20	Nuria Garcia, Cartif, Spain	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
130	12.05.20	Bart VAN DER BURG, BioDetectionSystems, The Netherlands	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
131	12.05.20	Mahmoud HAMZAOU, CELABOR srl, Belgium	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
132	12.05.20	Lara Lamon, Ca Foscari - University of Venice, Italy	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
133	12.05.20	Natividad Pérez, Andalusia Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Sustainable Development, Spain	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
134	12.05.20	Serge Creutz, Dow Europe GmbH, Germany	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
135	12.05.20	Marcel Van Berkel, Biobased Delta, The Netherlands	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
136	12.05.20	Margarita de Gregorio, BIOPLAT - Spanish Technology and	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020

Innovation Platform "Biomass for the Bioeconomy, Spain				
137	12.05.20	Nina Meglič, Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Štajerska, Slovenia	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
138	12.05.20	Ioannis Pavlidis, University of Crete, Greece	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
139	12.05.20	Rene van Ree, Wageningen University, The Netherlands	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
140	12.05.20	Arnaud Gasnier, Patentopolis, The Netherlands	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
141	12.05.20	Panagiotis Zervas, SCiO - Big data analytics in food systems, Greece	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
142	12.05.20	Monica Queseda Pena, Spanish Bank of Algae, Spain	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
143	12.05.20	Rodrigo Arandi, Greenwin, Belgium	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
144	12.05.20	Maria Teresa Lopez-Cerro, Leitat Technological Center, Spain	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
145	12.05.20	Lara Valentin, Funditec, Spain	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
146	12.05.20	Marion Potier, Wagralim ASBL, Belgium	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
147	12.05.20	Soumya Kanti Datta, Digiotech, Estonia	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
149	12.05.20	Kira Lenz, Berlin Partner für Wirtschaft und Technologie, Germany	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
150	12.05.20	Juan Riaza, ICAMYL, Spain	Online (scheduled)	BBI JU Info day 2020
151	28.05.20	(estimated +10-20 contacts)	Online (scheduled)	eWorkshop on Upcycled proteins

3.D.1.Target audience - Research and scientific community

Dissemination activity	Pre-market stimulation activities The consortium partners will organise a series of activities to support pre-market dissemination of the project results targeted at a range of chemical companies and manufacturers of end products (e.g. food, feeds, proteins, antioxidants, adhesives, resins, etc). Technology demonstrator events will be held at the industrial partners various sites, press releases will be made available on the project website and distributed to trade journals and brochures prepared detailing the Pro-Enrich developments in materials and the provision of bio-derived sustainable solutions.
Start month:	20
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of activities organised
Target Value	>5 activities
Lead Partner	Agro Business Park
Contributing Partners	Innovarum, Bangor University and InnoRenew in close collaboration with local industry partners

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT				
ACTIVITY NO.	WHEN*	WHO	WHERE	WHAT
1	30.06.21	FBCD/DTI /NTC	Webinar	Upcycling citrus and tomato biomass for high value applications
2	01.07.21	FBCD/DTI /GEA	Webinar	Processing of rapeseed meal and other raw materials for protein extraction
3	06.07.21	FBCD/DTI /CHI	Webinar	Replacing petrochemicals in adhesives – Our experience with rapeseed protein
4	12.07.21	FBCD/DTI/ T&L	Webinar	Upcycling food waste into new proteins and functional ingredients
5	14.10.21	FBCD/DTI/ EML/INR/ GEA/CHI/ T&L/NTC/BU	DTI, Taastrup & online	From residue to revenue – Scaling up biosolutions

4.A. Target audience - Existing networks

Dissemination activity	Networking, delivery of ad hoc newsletters, contribution to the existing newsletters List of networks relevant networks: ESWET; EIP-AGRI; COPA-COGECA; RAMIRAN (part of the ESCORENA network); CGIAR – FAO; GBEP - Global Bioenergy Partnership; The Knowledge Centre for Agriculture; International Network for Environmental management (INEM). Innovation network for biomass (INBIOM), FOODNETWORK
Start month:	4
Indicator to measure the impact	No. of connections
Target Value	At least 15 new connections established
Lead Partner	Innovarum
Contributing Partners	Agro Business Park, DTI, Bangor University, InnoRenew

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

CONNECTION NO.	WHEN*	WHO	CONNECTION	WHAT
1	18-05-2018	ABP	Innovation network for Bioresources	Pro-Enrich project description in "Innovation Network for Bioresources" newsletter
2	31-08-2018	DTI	Environment Technology Associations (DETA)	Partnership on sustainable biorefining
3	06-11-2018	ABP	Network for polymers	Presentation of Pro-Enrich at "Network for polymers" meeting
4	06-12-2018	BU	Biocomposites Centre's Annual Report 2018	Overview of the Pro-Enrich project
5	07-02-2019	BU	North Wales Economic Ambition Board (NWEAB)	Pro-Enrich case study in North Wales Economic Ambition Board (NWEAB) newsletter
6	20-02-2019	ABP	COPA-COGECA	Joint ABP/DTI/COPA-COGECA presentation at Bio-Based Industries Consortium - Matchmaking Event 2019
7	15-04-2019	INV	Agripa	Project page
8	15-04-2019	INV	Chil.org	Project page
9	14-06-2019	ABP	United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)	Network meeting with the UNDP Nordic Representation Office, at the "UN City" in Copenhagen
10	31-07-2019	ABP+DTI	LIAISON	Interview with LIAISON H2020 project

11	12-08-2019	BU	Welsh Government	Pro-Enrich promoted in Welsh government - e-News Bulletin - Horizon 2020
12	04-11-2019	BU	North Wales Regional Engagement Team	Pro-Enrich promoted in North Wales Regional Engagement Team ERDF Autumn Edition Newsletter
13	28-10-2019		Innovation network for Bioresources	Pro-Enrich project featured in "Innovation Network for Bioresources" newsletter
14	30-04-2020	INV	Application to EUBioNet Network	Networking. Project page-Newsletter
15	01-05-2020	INV	Application to Biorefine Cluster Europe	Networking. Project page-Newsletter
16	02-05-2020	INV	Application to EIP-Agri, Project Page	Networking. Project page-Newsletter
	01-07-2020	INV	Contact with DTI, Natac, Chimar, Mars: request/organise Newsletter contribution	
17	16-09-2020	BU	Info about final event	European Regions and Innovation Network website

5.A. Target audience - Political organizations

Dissemination activity	Direct contacts, personal invitations, conferences and other events The focus will be on regional, national and EU levels by targeting ministries, regional authorities and EU wide organisations. The entry point will be contacts already established by the various partners with their local political networks for example: the Ministry of Research and Innovation in Denmark, Expert Groups, etc.
Start month:	12
Indicator to measure the impact	Media coverage, keynote speech >2 political representatives participate in the project related events.
Target Value	
Lead Partner	DTI
Contributing Partners	Agro Business Park, Innovarum, Bangor University, InnoRenew
Additional Informatino	DTI will be assisted by following local partners: Agro Business Park (North), Innovarum (South), Bangor University (West) and InnoRenew (East)

STATUS AT THE END OF THE PROJECT

REPRESENTATIVE NO.	WHEN*	WHO	REPRESENTATIVE	WHAT
1	M6	BU	Peter Halligan and Robert Hoyle (Dr. Robert Hoyle, Chief Scientific Officer, Welsh Government Office for Science, Department for Economy and Transport, Welsh Government)	Meeting and discussion + poster presentation
2	M9	BU	Geographical Lead Officers Steve Davies (India and the Middle East), Jon Fitzgerald (North America & Europe) and Stuart Lyden (China & Japan).	Presentation to staff from the Welsh Government - International Relations Office. This included the Geographical Lead Officers Steve Davies (India and the Middle East), Jon Fitzgerald (North America & Europe) and Stuart Lyden (China & Japan).
3	20.05.2019	DTI	Delegation headed by Signe Lerche, Head of section, Ministry of Energy, Utilities and Climate	PowerPoint presentation of DTI activities regarding biorefining including Pro-Enrich as a case. Furthermore, visit to the pilot-scale biorefinery.
4	29.05.2019	EML	Visit by Mai Mercado, Minister for Children and Social Security	Visit by the Danish minister for Children and Social Security, Mai Mercado. The visit included a PowerPoint presentation showcasing the Pro-Enrich project.
5	08.10.19	DTI	Delegation from Ministry of Higher Education & Science	Tour of biorefinery plant and presentation that included information about Pro-Enrich.
6	05.11.20	FBCD	Morten Løkkegaard, Danish EU parliament member for the party Venstre	Presentation about DFBC's activities, BBI and how EU can be a catalyst for innovation, cooperation and partnership.
7	10.11.20	FBCD	Søren Gaard, director of business economy, The Danish Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs	Interview about new trends and challenges facing the food & bioresource industry in DK. Analysis is part of research for future policy initiatives for clusters in DK. Pro-Enrich used as an example of sustainable, climate-friendly protein production reducing the carbon footprint of e.g. pet food.

Annex 4 - Templates for harmonising dissemination and communication activities

Template for deliverables

D x.x: *title of the deliverable*

Acronym	Pro-Enrich		
Title	“Development of novel functional proteins and bioactive ingredients from rapeseed, olive, tomato and citrus fruit side streams for applications in food, cosmetics, pet food and adhesives”		
Grant agreement number	792050		
Call	H2020-BBI-JTI-2017 (BIO BASED INDUSTRIES PPP)		
Project coordinator	Danish Technological Institute (DTI)		
Topic	BBI.2017.R4		
Type of action	BBI-RIA		
Document Type (R/DEM/DEC/OTHER)	xxx		
Dissemination Level (PU/CO/CI)	xxx		
Leading partner	xxx		
Contributing partners	xxx		
Due date of delivery	xxx	Submission date	xxx

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“This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 792050”

This document reflects the views of the author(s) and does not necessarily reflect the views or policy of the European Commission. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the BBI-JU shall not be liable for any errors or omissions, however caused.

Document information

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V1		Dates stated in the Grant Agreement	

Additional author(s) and contribution	
Name	Organisation

Approved by:			
Issue	Date	Name	Organisation

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Executive summary

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Subsection

2.0 Section 1

2.1 Subsection

3.0 Section 2

....

4.0 Conclusions

Template for PowerPoint presentations

TITLE OF THE PRESENTATION

Name of speaker
speaker@mail.com

Logo of the
speaker's
institution

Event name.....
Venue....., date.....

Title of the slide

Ending slide: questions / Thanks for your attention, etc...

Contact of the speaker

Website address of the project

Twitter / Facebook of the project

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Template for Meetings' Agenda

**Pro-Enrich Project
Agenda**

Date:		Time:	
Scribe:		Place:	
Attendees:			

Agenda

Template for Meetings' Minutes

**Pro-Enrich Project
Meeting minutes**

Date:		Time:	
Scribe:		Place:	
Attendees:			

Meeting minutes:

Template for Posters at Congresses and Fairs

Development of novel functional proteins and bioactive ingredients from rapeseed, olive, tomato and citrus fruit side streams for applications in food, cosmetics, pet food and adhesives

Agricultural residues:
pressed olive pomace
olive mill waste water
rapeseed meal pressed cake
tomato and citrus fruit side streams

**FLEXIBLE
BIOREFINERY**

Proteins
Polyphenols
Dietary fibres
Pigments

**NEW
PRODUCT**

Industrial products

**MARKET
KEY AREAS**

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Contribute to fulfilling the growing global demand for alternative sources of protein and phenolic product stream through development of a bio-refinery approach enabling to recover high-purity functional bioactive compounds

EXPECTED IMPACTS

- ✓ Create new cross-sector interconnections in bio-based economy clusters
- ✓ Introduce the processing residues as valuable bio-refining resources
- ✓ Develop protocols for producing four different ingredients with purity levels enabling their use in foods, pet foods, cosmetics and adhesives
- ✓ Define how to adapt modern bio-refineries to seasonal residues within the same processing unit, reducing downtime and increasing return on investment
- ✓ Apply a circular and cascading biorefinery approach to feedstocks environmentally and economically sustainable, including a reduction in carbon footprint over existing processes of at least 10%

<p>Call: Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking JTI-2017.</p> <p>Total Budget: 3.9 M€</p> <p>Duration: 36 months (May '18 – April '21)</p> <p>Consortium: 16 partners from seven countries (ES, DK, UK, SI, DE, FR, EL)</p>	<p>Project Coordinator Anne Christine Sleenkjaer Hastrup Danish Technological Institute ach@dti.dk</p>	<p>Dissemination Manager Keli Andersen Agro Business Park kam@agropark.dk</p>
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www.PRO-ENRICH.eu

This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 792050.

Annex 5 - Data Management Plan

Project⁴ Number: 792050

Project Acronym: Pro-Enrich

Project title: Development of novel functional proteins and bioactive ingredients from rapeseed, olive, tomato and citrus fruit side streams for applications in food, cosmetics, pet food and adhesives

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

⁴ The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

Document information

Document history			
Issue	Date	Comment	Lead author
1.0	02.03.2020	1 st Draft	Natanya Majbritt Louie Hansen Danish Technological Institute nmlh@teknologisk.dk +45 7220 1106

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Name	Organisation
Anne Christine Steenkjær Hastrup acha@teknologisk.dk	DTI
Kell Andersen kan@agropark.dk	Agro Business Park

Approved by:			
Issue	Date	Name	Organisation
1.0	05.03.2020	Anne Christine Steenkjær Hastrup acha@teknologisk.dk	Danish Technological Institute +45 72201602

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Data Summary

Purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project

The purpose of data generation and collection is to support the development of the flexible biorefinery process outlined in the project objectives. To this end, data is generated at laboratory scale, which supports further development at pilot scale, generating further data. To support development and optimization of process protocols data is additionally collected from the literature regarding the targeted feedstocks as well as related residuals, including previous processing methodologies and results (yields, recovery rates etc.).

Types and formats of data

The project will generate and collect a wide range of data in the form of 1) biomass processing at laboratory, pilot and semi-industrial scale (methods and outcomes), 2) analysis methods, 3) literature reviews, 4) legislation reviews, 5) market analysis, 6) performance assessments from end users.

Re-use of existing data

The project will re-use existing data from the literature in the form of methodologies for biorefining such as enzymatic treatment, separation methods and analytical tools. Data re-use will comprise the basis for the development of the biorefinery processes of the feedstocks.

The size of the data

The size of data generated is currently unknown and difficult to predict.

Data utility

The data will provide a knowledge platform for stakeholders in the area of biorefining including research institutes, universities, primary producers, biotechnology processes and the biomass industry.

FAIR data

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data which can be made accessible within the limits of the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Data will be made findable and accessible by uploading through Zenodo. The upload to Zenodo ensures that the data produced will get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make it easily and uniquely citeable.

Standard chemical and taxonomic naming conventions will be followed.

Every set of data uploaded to Zenodo will contain searchable keywords.

Deliverables will contain version numbers.

Metadata standards will follow the directory from Horizon 2020 online manual.

Making data openly accessible

Restrictions to access in the data managed by Pro-Enrich comply with the IPR standards set by the consortium (D7.5: Exploitation & IPR Strategy) as well as H2020 principles on open access research (as open as possible and as closed as necessary). To ensure competitiveness and enhance the market potential of the products along with the processes developed in the project, restrictions to data may be required. The Exploitation Manager will assist relevant partners to oversee the process to ensure that both dissemination and exploitation proceed in compliance with the conditions defined in the grant agreement, the consortium agreement, and the plan for dissemination and exploitation along with the Exploitation & IPR Strategy (D7.5).

As a default, all public deliverables according to the General Agreement will be made openly available.

Data, which can be made accessible within the limits of the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, will be made findable and accessible by uploading through Zenodo.

A Pro-Enrich community has been set-up at Zenodo at the following URL:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/pro-enrich/?page=1&size=20>

No specific software will be needed to access the data. Data can be accessed through a web browser.

Access to public data will not be restricted and there is no need for a data access committee.

Making data interoperable

The open access data produced in the project will be interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. and adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible i.e. compliant with available (open) software applications.

Data will mainly be made available in standard software formats such as .wrd, .excl, .pdf.

Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Data which can be made accessible within the limits of the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement will be made findable and accessible without license by uploading through Zenodo.

The data will remain re-useable with an indefinite time frame.

Zenodo is hosted by CERN which has existed since 1954 and currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20+ years.

Data quality assurance is secured by internal review. Only data which has passed the internal quality review will be made available.

Allocation of resources

There are no costs associated with making data FAIR in Pro-Enrich. Upload to Zenodo is free.

The Coordinator of the project will be responsible for the overall data management in Pro-Enrich. Each partner is responsible for delivering generated data to the coordinator.

Data security

The following provisions are in place for open access data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage). Open access data is stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation.

Open Access Data:

Zenodo is considered by the project to be a secure place for data storage. The security provisions for Zenodo is described on the Zenodo website:

Zenodo servers are managed via [OpenStack](#) and [Puppet](#) configuration management system which ensures that our servers always have the latest security patches applied. Servers are monitored via CERN's monitoring infrastructure based on Flume, Elasticsearch, Kibana and Hadoop. Application errors are logged and aggregated in a local [Sentry](#) instance. Traffic to Zenodo frontend servers is load balanced via a combination of DNS load balancing and HAProxy load balancers.

Zenodo take security very serious and do our best to protect your data.

- *CERN Data Centre: Our data centres is located on CERN premises and all physical access is restricted to a limited number of staff with appropriate training and who have been granted access in line with their professional duties (e.g. Zenodo staff do not have physical access to the CERN Data Centre) .*
- *Servers: Our servers are managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers, meaning e.g. remote access to our servers are restricted to Zenodo staff with appropriate training, and the operating system and installed applications are kept updated with latest security patches via our automatic configuration management system Puppet.*
- *Network: CERN Security Team runs both host and network based intrusion detection systems and monitors the traffic flow, pattern and contents into and out of CERN networks in order to detect attacks. All access to zenodo.org happens over HTTPS, except for static documentation pages which are hosted on GitHub Pages.*
- *Data: Zenodo stores user passwords using strong cryptographic password hashing algorithms (currently PBKDF2+SHA512). Users' access tokens to GitHub and ORCID are stored encrypted and can only be decrypted with the application's secret key.*
- *Application: We are employing a suite of techniques to protect your session from being stolen by an attacker when you are logged in and run vulnerability scans against the application.*

- *Staff: CERN staff with access to user data operate under [CERN Operational Circular no. 5](#), meaning among other things that*
 - *staff should not exchange among themselves information acquired unless it is expressly required for the execution of their duties.*
 - *access to user data must always be consistent with the professional duties and only permitted for resolution of problems, detection of security issues, monitoring of resources and similar.*
 - *staff are liable for damage resulting from any infringement and can have access withdrawn and/or be subject to disciplinary or legal proceedings depending on seriousness of the infringement.*

For non-open access data, data security is managed individually by project partners which are each responsible for maintaining data security within the realms that they control. A collaborative platform (MS TEAMS) has been set-up to handle data exchange necessary for project collaboration. DTI handles data necessary for project management and communication on their own servers. Data communicated to the EU such as project deliverables and other information requested by the EU is submitted and stored on servers of the EU.

Ethical aspects

Pro-Enrich does not include personal data.

Other issues

None

Annex 6 – Final event programme

From residue to revenue - Scaling up bio-solutions

14 October, 2021 at 09:30 - 15:30

PROGRAMME

<p>09:30 Registration, coffee and networking</p> <hr/> <p>10:00 Welcome <i>By Anne Christine Steenkjær Hastrup, Director at bioresources and biorefining, Danish Technological Institute & Lars Hørsholt Jensen</i></p> <hr/> <p>10:10 ECBF - A new Growth Stage Fund focused on the European Bioeconomy <i>By Michael Nettersheim, Managing Partner, European Circular Bioeconomy Fund</i></p> <hr/> <p>10:35 Industrializing Biorefinery Processes: Possibilities at DTI pilot plant with Pro-Enrich as the main case <i>By Anne Christine Steenkjær Hastrup, Danish Technological Institute</i></p> <hr/> <p>11:00 Break</p> <hr/> <p>11:10 Technical solutions for vegetable protein processing <i>By Dominik Krienke, process engineer, GEA</i></p> <hr/> <p>11:30 Large scale production of plant-based botanical ingredients - the case of Natac Biotech <i>By Jose Maria Pinilla, R&D Project Manager, Natac Biotech</i></p>	<p>11:55 Break</p> <hr/> <p>12:15 Panel debate with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nelo Emerencia - Director Programming, Bio-based Industries Consortium • Michael Nettersheim - Managing partner, European Circular Bioeconomy Fund • Eric-Allan Rapp - Partner, AgriFood Investments - Vækstfonden • Katrine Hvid Ellegård - Business Development & Innovation Consultant • Mathias Greve-Poulsen - Research chemist, KMC Ingredients • Anne Christine Steenkjær Hastrup - Danish Technological Institute • Ole Kaae Hansen - Owner, OK BIOTECH <hr/> <p>13:00 Conclusions of the day <i>By Anne Christine Steenkjær Hastrup, Danish Technological Institute</i></p> <hr/> <p>13:15 Lunch and end of virtual event</p> <hr/> <p>14:00 Guided tours to Pro-Enrich partner stands and pilot plant + networking</p> <hr/> <p>15:30 End of event</p>
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This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 792050.

Pro-Enrich: Development of novel functional proteins and bioactive ingredients from rapeseed, olive, tomato and citrus fruit side streams for applications in food, cosmetics, pet food and adhesives

“This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 792050”

Project partners at the end of the project

<p>Danish Technological Institute Denmark www.dti.dk</p>	<p>Bangor University United Kingdom www.bc.bangor.ac.uk</p>	<p>Innorenew Slovenia www.innorenew.eu</p>	<p>GEA Germany www.gea.com/en</p>
<p>Anecoop Spain www.anecoop.com</p>	<p>Tailorzyme Denmark www.tailorzyme.com</p>	<p>Food & Bio Cluster Denmark Denmark www.foodbiocluster.dk</p>	<p>Emmelev Denmark www.emmelev.dk</p>
<p>Marzi Franka</p>	<p>JAENCOOP grupo</p>		
<p>Marzi Franka Slovenia</p>	<p>Chimar Greece www.chimarhellas.com</p>	<p>Innovarum Spain www.innovarum.es</p>	<p>JAENCOOP Spain www.jaencoop.com</p>
<p>LEITAT <small>managing technologies</small></p>			
<p>Mars Germany www.mars.com</p>	<p>Natac Spain www.natacgroup.com</p>	<p>Tate & Lyle United Kingdom www.tateandlyle.com</p>	<p>Leitat Spain www.leitat.org</p>